

UWS-Oxfam Partnership: Collaborative Research Reports Series
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On Target for 2030?

An independent snapshot review of Scotland's progress against the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals

**SUSTAINABLE
DEVELOPMENT
GOALS**

Report editors: Hartwig Pautz*, Oudai Tozan and Paul Bradley*****

*** University of the West of Scotland, ** Oxfam Scotland,
*** Scottish Council for Voluntary Organisations**

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The UWS-Oxfam Partnership: 'For a more equitable and sustainable Scotland'.

The UWS-Oxfam Partnership is a formally established relationship between the University of the West of Scotland and Oxfam Scotland, underpinned by a Memorandum of Understanding. The Partnership emerged in 2011/12 as a result of prior collaborative work between UWS staff and Oxfam and its then community partner organisations, revolving around the development of Oxfam's anti-poverty advocacy and campaigning in Scotland. The Partnership has comprised:

- A Research and Knowledge Exchange linking UWS academics, Oxfam Scotland and community organisations in collaborative projects;
- A limited programme of placements and work-related learning and volunteering opportunities, enabling UWS students to contribute to the work of Oxfam and community organisations, while developing their experience and skills;
- The UWS-Oxfam Policy Forum, which brings all of these partners together with a broad range of external organisations from across all sectors of Scottish society, to discuss key questions and to inform understanding and engagement with both existing and emergent issues.

The Partnership publishes a series of Collaborative Research Reports, available from the Partnership's website – www.uwsoxfampartnership.org.uk.

About the report editors

Dr Hartwig Pautz is Lecturer in Social Sciences at the University of the West of Scotland and has been working with the UWS-Oxfam Partnership in a leading position for a number of years.

Oudai Tozan is Project Officer at Oxfam Scotland and has supported Oxfam in its wider campaigning and influencing projects.

Paul Bradley is Policy and Campaigns Officer at the Scottish Council for Voluntary Organisations (SCVO) and is responsible for coordinating the SDG Network Scotland, an open coalition that seeks to champion and secure progress on the Sustainable Development Goals in Scotland.

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Introduction

The Sustainable Development Goals — a global strategy

In 2015, the Member States of the United Nations (UN) unanimously adopted the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)¹ – an ambitious roadmap for a healthy planet for present and future generations and for a world free from poverty, injustice and discrimination. In many ways, the SDGs are the closest the world has yet come to a strategy for ending extreme poverty, tackling inequalities, and combatting climate change. The seventeen Goals, which are at the heart of the Agenda for Sustainable Development,² are to be achieved by 2030. They are global in scope and apply, unlike the preceding UN Millennium Development Goals from 2000, to each UN Member State. That means that now over 190 countries are committed to taking action to realise the Goals at home as well as abroad. The seventeen SDGs, with their 169 Goal Targets and many more associated Goal Indicators, are complex in their ambition and are achievable only if all countries, sectors and citizens invest significant effort and embark on the ‘SDG journey’ together.

Even before the UN formally ratified the Goals in September 2015, Scotland’s First Minister announced that Scotland would become one of the first nations to adopt the SDGs and promised to provide international leadership.³ While recognising the Goals are global in nature, four years on, the time has come to assess whether this strong commitment has led to real progress towards achieving the ambitious targets by 2030 in Scotland itself. This report – *On Target for 2030? An independent snapshot review of Scotland’s progress against the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals* – offers a collective contribution from Scottish civil society organisations, helping to answer the question of whether Scotland is making progress towards achieving the SDGs, whether it has the right strategies, and whether things could be done differently and better.

Success in achieving the Goals requires country-specific assessment and evaluation in order to understand where action is needed, whether progress is being made, and what obstacles may lie in the way. For this reason, the Goals are linked to Goal Targets with associated Indicators to help identify national challenges and priorities and to track progress. These Targets and Indicators are also important for holding not only governments, but also key stakeholders from the private and third sectors to account, and to help ensure a collective responsibility across both state and society to contribute to international progress.

With regards to reporting progress or otherwise towards the Goals, all UN Member States have agreed to an official reporting mechanism. As outlined in more detail in the next section, the UK will submit its first ‘Voluntary National Review’ (VNR) to the UN in summer 2019. Given its early and enthusiastic endorsement of the Goals, the Scottish Government is also undertaking its own assessment and will, around the same time, publish its ‘Supplementary Review’ to chart Scotland’s progress. This review is developed collaboratively with the SDG Network Scotland.⁴ Therefore, *On Target for 2030?* is just one of several attempts to evaluate progress towards the SDGs. However, it is special in a particular way. It is a compilation of independent assessments provided by no less than 22 civil society organisations and has been produced – under the auspices of the UWS-Oxfam Partnership and in collaboration with the Scottish Council for Voluntary Organisations (SCVO) as host of the SDG Network Scotland – without any government involvement. It is also important to note that there has been only minimal editorial input into the assessments, so that they truly reflect the views and voices of those who wrote them. At the same time, and because of its very nature, the ‘snapshot review’ does not claim to be a comprehensive assessment of ‘how Scotland is doing’, hence its name. Compiled to

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coincide with the publication of the UK Government and Scottish Government reviews, the snapshot review should add a valuable element to the overall evaluation of how far Scotland has come and what remains to be done.

Assessing success: the UK Voluntary National Review and the Scottish Supplementary Review

All UN Member States are expected, at least once, to review national progress towards the SDGs and to present a report to the UN High Level Political Forum (HLPF). This Voluntary National Review (VNR) is a key part of Agenda 2030 and, while reviews are expected to cover all seventeen Goals, each HLPF has a theme set to encourage some greater focus on a smaller selection of the Goals each year. The theme for 2019 is 'Empowering people and ensuring inclusiveness and equality', and the specific Goals to be reviewed in depth are Quality Education; Decent Work; Reduced Inequality; Climate Action; Peace, Justice and Strong Institutions; and Partnerships. *On Target for 2030?* has partly replicated this focus, as it provides two assessments on each of four of these Goals.

For the VNR, the UK Government began its stakeholder engagement with devolved UK administrations (in Scotland, Wales and Northern Ireland), businesses, and civil society in autumn 2018, and then published its Summary of Main Messages in May 2019. The Government hopes that the UK VNR will outline collective effort and action across England, Scotland, Wales and Northern Ireland to show how the UK is contributing to the SDGs across the world, and also in the UK itself.⁵ At the same time, the UK Parliament's International Development Committee (IDC) is also conducting an inquiry into UK progress on the SDGs and will publish the outcomes in summer 2019; the inquiry is likely to come to a critical verdict as, in April 2019, the IDC published a letter to the then Secretary of State for International Development in which it highlighted concerns about the ability of the UK's VNR process to capture meaningful evidence on SDGs progress. Specifically, these concerns included the compressed timeline for the VNR, as well as the lack of meaningful stakeholder engagement, and also limited coordination across government.⁶ Beyond such governmental and parliamentary scrutiny, Bond – the UK-based network of organisations working in international development – published in June 2019 a report examining the UK's global contribution to the SDGs. Compiled by 49 organisations and fourteen networks and working groups, the report highlights 'crucial gaps where attention and investment are most needed'.⁷

As indicated above, the Scottish Government has been a vocal supporter of the SDGs. While the 1999 devolution settlement has given the Scottish Parliament significant powers, some crucial policy areas relevant to the SDGs remain reserved to the UK Parliament. Nonetheless, since the 2018 redesign of the Scottish Government's National Performance Framework (NPF),⁸ which sets out a vision for Scotland through eleven National Outcomes and many associated indicators, the SDGs now map onto specific outcomes and align with their indicators, so that it could be argued that the SDGs are placed at the very heart of how Scotland measures its own broad progress. While the redesign of the NPF will make measuring success or failure in achieving the SDGs easier, the Scottish Government also commissioned Dr Graham Long of Newcastle University to undertake an initial analysis of how Scotland itself appears through the lens of the SDGs. This analysis aimed to assess aspects of the alignment between Scotland's data gathering and governance and the SDG Targets and Indicators, and also the relevance of the Goals for the specific Scottish context and for the National Outcomes of the NPF. The report, published in 2019, suggests that performance in Scotland across the SDG Targets, where data is available, has been 'broadly

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comparable to the UK as a whole, though with some more positive areas, and some that are less positive’.⁹

Further evaluation efforts are being made by the SDG Network Scotland. In September 2018, the Network – an open coalition bringing together the voices of over 300 people and organisations – facilitated the creation of an open VNR Working Group, aiming to ensure that the voices of those committed to sustainability would be heard by the Scottish Government and be captured in Scotland’s contribution to the UK Government’s VNR. The group was joined by the Scottish Government and the Convention of Scottish Local Authorities (CoSLA) in October 2018. Since then, Scotland’s contribution to the UK VNR and its own Supplementary Review have been developed collaboratively and openly with Network members and wider civil society. This approach has been broadly welcomed, but with the Scottish Government as the lead author for this report, it is also important for civil society to have its own space to evaluate progress independently.

The ‘snapshot review’ — approach and rationale

As stated above, this snapshot review’s particular contribution focusses solely on Scotland and does so by giving space for Scottish civil society organisations’ own independent assessments. The review, *On Target for 2030?*, is not the first to take this approach, but it is the first to do so focussing on Scotland. For the UK level, the UK Stakeholders for Sustainable Development (UKSSD) have already reported, using a traffic light scheme to flag up success or failure. They found that for the 143 relevant targets, ‘the UK is performing well on 24% (green), with 57% where there are gaps in policy coverage or performance is not adequate (amber), and [for] 15% [...] there is little or no policy in place to address the target or the performance is poor (red)’.¹⁰

Because the explicit aim of this report is to give relevant civil society organisations space to voice their own assessments, its editors have kept their input to a minimum. Their role was to contact organisations felt most likely to have an interest in contributing to the review on a specific Goal and to send contributors a simple template – provided in the Annex of this report – to guide their submissions. The template provided space for:

- a paragraph about the contributing organisation;
- an assessment of how Scotland was moving towards the specific SDG;
- an evaluation of the existing strength of policy commitment to achieving the SDG in Scotland;
- a summary of what should be done to achieve the Goal by 2030.

Contributors were also asked to provide a case study to exemplify how their organisation may contribute to achieving the relevant Goal, or how communities or individuals are affected by the lack of progress towards that Goal. The template sought a response of no more than two pages. As readers will see, many contributions are rather longer. This shows two things – first, that contributors had a lot more they wanted to say; second, that the editors were prepared to respect and to accommodate that. Without commenting on wider approaches, the editors decided not to ask contributors to ‘rate’ progress through a traffic light scheme, so as to do justice to the complexity of the Goals and to what is involved in their assessments.

The editors subsequently liaised with the contributors over any stylistic changes and anything that seemed in need of clarification or further detail. The editors also circulated

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many of the contributions to the SDG Network Scotland to elicit feedback and commentary from its members. Where feedback was received, it was relayed to the contributing organisations prior to finalising their assessment. Finally, it is important to note that the editors refrained from writing a 'conclusion' or an 'executive summary'. The reason was that the snapshot review was to bring together the views of a wide range of civil society organisations and not to be about what the editors might make of them. Also, the complex nature of the Goals and their individual assessments would have made a general summary problematic, and may have meant the editors bringing too much of their own interpretations and interest into the report.

On Target for 2030? is called a 'snapshot review' because it makes no claim to comprehensively represent 'Scottish civil society', but rather gives space to organisations which responded positively to the editors' initial request. These were sometimes organisations already involved in the SDG Network, but for the greater part the editors succeeded in getting organisations to contribute to the review which had not previously been involved in discussions around the SDGs. It is also a 'snapshot' because the report does not present a comprehensive and technical assessment of all Indicators under each Goal, but gathers views and perspectives from civil society organisations on progress in areas of their specific interest and involvement. This explains why some assessments only focus on some aspects of a Goal, aspects core to what the contributing organisations are all about.

The contributors are organisations from across Scotland as a whole, although many are, understandably, based in the 'central belt' between Edinburgh and Glasgow. They range from large organisations to those with only a few paid staff, and include some organisations with a local focus, whilst the majority carry out their day-to-day activities with a view to the whole of Scotland. The editors initially contacted many more organisations than the 22 whose assessments are presented in the report. They found that while many were interested in participating, often only those with a good number of paid staff had the resources to do so. But the enthusiastic engagement from so many organisations was testament to the importance of the SDGs as a yardstick for developed countries and also to Scottish civil society's willingness to engage with vital and larger social, economic, cultural and environmental questions.

Working towards achieving the SDGs in Scotland

While the editors have decided not to write a summary of the report, for the reasons outlined above, they considered it important to flag up a few themes which are shared by all or most contributions.

- Many contributors conclude that whilst there is clear policy and political commitment on all of the Goals in Scotland, more needs to be done in order to meet the 2030 targets;
- Poverty and inequality provide a thread that runs through many contributions. This is an important theme, given the 'leave no-one behind' focus of the SDGs;¹¹
- It is not just up to the Scottish and UK Governments to deliver on the Goals – what is needed is coordinated action also from business, the third sector and citizens to deliver progress;
- Many contributions emphasise the importance of the participation of citizens in developing policy solutions;
- There is a lack of available, high-quality Scotland-specific data in some policy areas;
- The NPF is a welcome mechanism for progressing the SDGs at a national level in

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Scotland. However, further work is needed to improve and build upon a fairly loose alignment of these national and international frameworks.

To conclude this Introduction, the editors hope that *On Target for 2030?* will contribute to the debate around progress towards the SDGs and around how Scotland can live up to the expectations created when the Scottish Government endorsed the Goals and later incorporated them into the NPF. Importantly, the assessments presented here do not simply ascribe all responsibility for achieving the Goals to 'the government'; instead they are often very nuanced in holding a mirror up to civil society itself and also, crucially, to the business sector. What is important to note as well is that the assessments do not suggest policy solutions that seem at all unrealistic or impossible. What is proposed is eminently 'doable', given the necessary political will and the sincere commitment of all stakeholders. The editors hope that the report's readers will include stakeholders who will consider both the assessments and the related policy recommendations with the seriousness they merit.

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⁸ Scottish Government. (2019) National Performance Framework. Online from <https://nationalperformance.gov.scot/>

⁹ Long, Graham. (2019) The SDGs and Scotland: a discussion paper and initial analysis. Online from <https://globalgoals.scot/wp-content/uploads/2019/02/SDG-Discussion-paper-February-2019.pdf>, p3

¹⁰ UKSSD. (2019) Measuring up. How the UK is performing on the UN Sustainable Development Goals. Online from <https://www.ukssd.co.uk/Handlers/Download.ashx?IDMF=62c71dd6-d83b-4b3b-b98b-e7f9f1e21907>

¹¹ UNDP. (2018) What does it mean to leave no one behind? A UNDP discussion paper and framework for implementation. July 2018. Online from <https://www.undp.org/content/undp/en/home/librarypage/poverty-reduction/what-does-it-mean-to-leave-no-one-behind-.html>

End poverty in all its forms everywhere

Child Poverty Action Group in Scotland

CPAG in Scotland was established in 1999 as the Scotland office of the Child Poverty Action Group. CPAG works to raise awareness of the impact of poverty on children; helps families to maximise their income by ensuring that they receive their full benefit entitlement; and campaigns for policy changes to end child poverty. CPAG does this through providing advice, information and training on benefits to organisations in Scotland as well as by promoting policy solutions with a positive impact on the lives of low-income families through campaign and policy work.

How is Scotland doing against this Goal?

Real progress was made toward ending poverty in Scotland, particularly child and pensioner poverty, between the mid-1990s and 2011/12. Child poverty rates fell from 33% (360,000 children) to 19% (190,000) children, pensioner poverty fell from 290 000 (33%) to 120,000 (12%) and poverty amongst all people fell from 25% to 16%.¹ This progress was achieved as a result of policy interventions resulting from a clear political commitment. Key interventions were put in place which were in keeping with later SDG Goal Target 1.3 regarding nationally appropriate social protection systems and measures. Amongst these interventions were the introduction of the National Minimum Wage and substantial increases in Universal Child Benefit as well as means-tested benefits for low-income families. Significant examples include increases in Income Support and the introduction and expansion of the tax credit system.² The initial UK Government target – the reduction of child poverty by one quarter by 2004/05 from its 1998/99 level – was only narrowly missed. Over the next three years, child poverty levels stopped falling and the 2010/11 target of reducing it by one half from its 1998/99 level was missed. Despite this, the number of children in relative poverty across the UK fell from 3.4 million in 1998/99 to 2.3 million in 2010/11.

Had this early commitment and momentum been maintained, the goal of halving the proportion of people living in poverty according to national definitions could feasibly have been met. However, poverty is now rising, especially amongst children. Almost one in four (240,000) of Scotland's children are now officially recognised as living in poverty. In the absence of significant policy change, this figure is likely to continue to increase in the coming years, with the Scottish Government's own forecasts indicating that it will reach 38% by 2030/31.³ Recent analysis by the Resolution Foundation also suggests the Scottish child poverty rate will be at 29% by 2023/24 – the highest rate in over twenty years.⁴ This would reverse the fall in child poverty observed in the UK since the late 1990s.⁵

These are not just statistics. These numbers are about children going hungry, missing out on school trips, and being unable to enjoy the activities and opportunities their better-off peers take for granted. These numbers tell stories about parents going without meals, juggling debt, and seeing their own health suffer to protect their children from the worst consequences of poverty. Yet, as progress from the mid-90s to early 2010s demonstrates, poverty is policy-sensitive and Scotland has many of the tools needed for positive change.

Is Scotland committed to achieving this Goal?

Scotland is showing evidence of real political and policy commitment to tackling child poverty. In 2017, the Child Poverty (Scotland) Act was passed unanimously by the Scottish Parliament, setting out ambitious targets to reduce child poverty by 2030. These targets are in line with the SDGs to halve the number of people living in poverty. With regard to implementing nationally appropriate social protection systems, as stipulated in Goal Target 1.3, the Scottish Government have outlined a range of measures as part of their first 'Tackling Child Poverty Delivery Plan'. Local authorities and health boards are also now under a statutory duty to deliver joint plans setting out how they tackle child poverty.

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Nationally, the Scottish Government have invested in 'Best Start Grants', which provide low-income families with financial support during the early years of a child's life. National and local government also work together to deliver a minimum payment of £100 for school clothing. As well as such policies, which put money directly into families' pockets, the 'Healthier Wealthier Children Programme' supports pregnant women and families with children at risk of, or experiencing poverty. The Programme seeks to do so by creating information and referral pathways between the National Health Service and money and welfare advice services. Early learning and childcare have also been expanded as part of an approach to reducing costs of childcare and removing barriers to paid work. Despite this, recent projections have outlined that Scotland is not nearly on target to reach its own child poverty goals.

Whilst there is no question that rising poverty is currently driven by UK Government social security cuts,⁶ there is a need for more urgency from Scottish Ministers in stemming rising poverty. The Scottish Government have committed to introducing a new Income Supplement for low-income families. This commitment demonstrates a welcome willingness to use new devolved social security powers to directly tackle poverty. It is a potential game-changer in terms of reversing the current child poverty trajectory, with indications that ministers expect the supplement to have a substantive impact on child poverty.⁷

However, currently the new scheme is not to start until 2022. Families struggling to properly feed and clothe their children now cannot wait that long. As time passes, childhoods slip by. These are childhoods blighted by the fact their families do not have the money they need to give their children a decent start in life. If the 2030 targets are to be met, substantive investment in support to restore adequate family incomes needs to start now.

What should Scotland do better to achieve this Goal?

The number one priority to help achieve SDG 1 must be the introduction of the new Income Supplement, or an interim measure, with absolute urgency. A £5 top-up to Child Benefit would be one simple way to start lifting thousands of children out of poverty and protecting many more. Of course, social security alone cannot tackle poverty as there is a huge range of factors that combine and result in family hardships. Efforts across local and national governments must continue to improve income from employment and to reduce childcare costs and overall living costs. But with 65% of children in poverty living in working families, it is clear that work is not a guaranteed route out of poverty in Scotland. As UK Government benefit cuts drive more and more families into hardship, the Scottish Parliament must use every tool in its toolbox to protect Scotland's children and meet its own statutory child poverty targets. Therefore, Scotland should renew its commitment to tackling poverty, in particular child poverty. Child poverty blights childhoods and has a lasting impact. Growing up in poverty means being cold, going hungry, and not being able to join in the activities so important for children. In a fair and just nation, it is not right that one in four of our children experiences poverty and its consequences – Scotland can and must do better.

Case study — how to detect poverty

The Early Warning System (EWS) was set up by CPAG in Scotland to collect and analyse case evidence about how changes to social security are affecting the wellbeing of children, their families and the communities and services that support them. Below are extracts from CPAG's most recent work with low-income families.

Many of the families say that they are not able to do activities with their children, take them

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on day trips, or treat them occasionally. This is having a detrimental impact on overall family well-being.

'[I would like] just being able to treat the kids to days out or, ken, they're talking about going to, 'oh we're going to the zoo this weekend, or I'm going to treat the bairns to, ken, we're going to go to Nando's or we're going to go to this place'. Like not even just that, just hearing that they're treating them. I'd just like to be able to do stuff like that'. (Claire)

Families also report high levels of anxiety and describe the impact of poverty on their mental health.

'[Living on a low income] It's horrible. It definitely is. I mean, apart from all the obvious anxiety triggers it gives me and the insomnia, it drags me down as a person, and it makes me a worse person. I lose my temper more easily, and things like that. I mean, yeah, 'cause I'm sleep-deprived I'm anxious and all those things as well, but generally across the board as well. Because it's a constant stress, am I going to make ends meet?'. (Sarah)

Author

John Dickie, Director of Child Poverty Action Group in Scotland

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² Joyce, Robert. (2014) Child poverty in Britain: recent trends and future prospects. IFS Working Paper W15/07. Online from <https://www.ifs.org.uk/uploads/publications/wps/WP201507.pdf>

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End hunger, achieve food security and improved nutrition and promote sustainable agriculture

Nourish Scotland

Nourish Scotland is a charity campaigning for a fairer and more sustainable food system. Established in 2013, we believe that only a transformation of the whole food system will result in effective and sustainable solutions. Our distinctive contribution is that we read across food issues – health, inequality and social justice, environmental justice, and the local food economy. We also link the levels, supporting grassroots community efforts and influencing national policy and legislation – using each to inform the other.

How is Scotland doing against this Goal?

Goal 2 covers several areas relevant to Scotland's food system. As with the SDGs more generally, responsibility for progress rests with several departments – including those responsible for social security; wages and working conditions; health; agriculture; and the environment. Scotland has made little substantive progress on Goal Target 2.1 which stipulates that, by 2030, hunger should have ended and that all people, in particular the poor and people in vulnerable situations (including infants), should have access to safe, nutritious and sufficient food all year round. The lack of progress is not only visible in the growing numbers of people in vulnerable situations who have to go to food banks. Behind them, around 8% of the Scottish population in 2017 described themselves as 'food insecure'.¹ This rises to over 20% for single parents and disabled people.² More broadly, while food in Scotland is generally safe, not enough is done to make nutritious food (e.g. fruit, vegetables, nuts and whole grains) accessible and affordable for all. That means that, for the past twenty years, we have made no progress in meeting the Scottish Dietary Goals – first published in 1996, before being updated in 2013 and 2016. Set at a population level, these goals indicate the extent of dietary change needed to reduce diet-related disease and obesity in Scotland. A key message of these goals is the reduction of calorie intake by 120kcal per person, per day.³ The proportion of babies being breastfed at 6–8 weeks of age has increased from 36% of babies born in 2001/02 to 42% of babies born in 2017/18.⁴ However, breastfeeding rates in Scotland remain low compared to those seen in other countries and fall far short of recommended levels.

Scotland has also made little progress in relation to Goal Indicator 2.2.2, on the prevalence of malnutrition. Specifically, Scotland has made little overall progress in reducing overweight among infants. In school year 2017/18, 76.5% of children measured in Primary 1 had a healthy weight, 22.4% were at risk of overweight or obesity and 1.1% were at risk of underweight.⁵ Since 2001/02, the overall proportion of Primary 1 children who are at risk of overweight or obesity has remained fairly constant, increasing in the most deprived areas but decreasing in the least deprived areas. Worryingly, there are now substantial inequalities in child unhealthy weight across Scotland.

Goal Target 2.3 is concerned with doubling agricultural productivity and the incomes of small-scale food producers, in particular women, indigenous peoples, family farmers, pastoralists and fishers, including through secure and equal access to land, other productive resources and inputs, knowledge, financial services, markets and opportunities for value addition and non-farm employment. Here, figures for Scotland are less detailed and reliable. What is clear is that the current farm support system excludes the smallest producers with less than three hectares. Securing access to land remains difficult. Efforts to make tenancies more secure have led to a reduction in the area of land available for rent. There are still gender inequalities in terms of access to land despite the formal end of primogeniture. Incomes of small farmers remain for the most part low, with most small farmers unable to draw the minimum wage from their business. There has been some

End hunger, achieve food security and improved nutrition and promote sustainable agriculture

support for farm diversification but little practical focus on supporting short food chains which benefit small-scale producers.

With regard to Goal Indicator 2.4.1 – which is about the proportion of agricultural area under productive and sustainable agriculture – we would question the sustainability of some widespread agricultural practices. The Scottish Environmental Protection Agency, Scotland’s environmental regulator, issue a range of licenses designed to control activities that could lead to pollution or environmental damage. At a follow-up visit, they have found that 50% of dairy farms are non-compliant with these licenses.⁶ Overuse of nitrogen fertiliser and pesticides has worsened over the last ten years. Scottish agriculture uses too much nitrogen fertiliser, which runs off from fields and affects the make-up of wild plants, with those that thrive in nutrient-rich environments becoming more dominant and others disappearing. 94% of Scotland’s soft fruit crops,⁷ and 98% of arable crops⁸ are sprayed with pesticides which have been linked to significant declines in bees and other pollinators, as well as birds and other wildlife. While environmental schemes are funded as part of the Rural Development Programme, the overall scale and impact of these is still small, with the bulk of farm support still provided on a land area basis without minimal requirements for sustainability. The proportion of Scotland’s farmland in organic management has fallen to 2%, one of the lowest proportions in the EU.

Is Scotland committed to achieving this Goal?

Scotland is a wealthy country, and commitment should be proportionate to available resources. The Scottish Government’s new Best Start Grant foods scheme is a welcome effort to make fruit and vegetable more available to babies and infants in low-income households, as is the provision for improving food in early learning and childcare. We would argue for widening eligibility for Best Start foods and for giving nutrition a higher priority across the range of services for children. We particularly welcome the commitment by Glasgow City Council to extend provision of free school meals initially to P4 children and eventually to all primary school pupils. There is Scottish Government policy commitment to ending the need for food banks, and the Scottish Welfare Fund provides cash Crisis Grants to people who have run out of money to buy food. The Fair Food Transformation Fund, until 2019, invested in dignified alternatives to food banks, and money has been allocated for holiday provision which will improve access to food in the holidays for some children. However, a sharper focus on upstream measures and a higher level of resources are needed, alongside a strategic plan to phase out the food bank model in Scotland.

There is not yet a formal commitment to reducing food insecurity, although there are commitments on child poverty and on fuel poverty. This needs to be put in place as part of the Good Food Nation bill. Bringing forward the Scottish Government’s plans for the Income Supplement to support single parent households would make a tangible difference.

While there is policy support for reducing childhood obesity, and the First Minister has committed to halving this by 2030, the lack of progress on this agenda in the last 20 years suggests that more of the same will not be enough to deliver this commitment. Much bolder action is needed, especially given the growing inequality between more and less affluent households.

There is limited Scottish Government policy support for sustainable agriculture, although a nitrogen budget is now being introduced. There is a degree of complacency about Scottish agriculture’s green credentials, and maintaining biodiversity is too often seen as an alternative to productive agriculture rather than an integral element. There has been no

End hunger, achieve food security and improved nutrition and promote sustainable agriculture

significant effort to reverse the decline in land under organic management, or to stimulate the organic supply chain either for export or for the UK market.

What should Scotland do better to achieve this Goal?

Implementing the 'right to food' as part of the Good Food Nation bill, along with duties on Scottish Ministers and public bodies would underpin progress on this Goal. The right-to-food framework would support greater policy coherence, monitoring and accountability across the food system. Government has to take the lead as some of the delivery of this Goal depends on significant changes by business, with regulation generally being the fairest and most effective way to make progress. However, the third sector – and in particular community organisations – can support shifts, for example, in parenting practices, and social enterprises can support short food chains and small producers. More generally, Scotland should look at best practice around the world and seek to match this. The Nordic countries present a convenient comparator, with much lower levels of childhood obesity, more sustainable farming practices, and minimal levels of food insecurity.

Further reading

- Fair Food Transformation Fund: <https://www2.gov.scot/Topics/People/fairerscotland/tacklingpovertyinScotland/food-poverty>
- Nourish Scotland's Food Atlas: http://www.nourishscotland.org/wp-content/uploads/2018/08/Food-Atlas_FINAL_online.pdf
- Scottish Government's Best Start Foods scheme: <https://www.mygov.scot/best-start-grant/>
- The Scottish Health Survey 2017: <https://www.gov.scot/publications/scottish-health-survey-2017-summary-key-findings/pages/7/>
- A Menu for Change: menuforchange.org.uk

Author

Pete Ritchie, Director of Nourish Scotland

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⁴ NHS Scotland and National Statistics. (2019) Infant Feeding Statistics Scotland, Financial Year of Birth 2017/2018. Online from <https://www.isdscotland.org/Health-Topics/Child-Health/Publications/2018-10-30/2018-10-30-Infant-Feeding-Summary.pdf?91334170104>

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⁶ SEPA. (2018) Dairy Production Sector Plan. Online from https://consultation.sepa.org.uk/sector-plan/dairy-production/user_uploads/dairy-production-sector-plan-1.pdf

⁷ Scottish Government. (2016) Pesticide usage in Scotland 2016. Online from <https://www.gov.scot/publications/pesticide-usage-scotland-soft-fruit-crops-2016/pages/2/>

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⁹ Scottish Government. (2016) Organic farming in Scotland: 2016 statistics. Online from <https://www.gov.scot/publications/organic-farming-scotland-2016-statistics/>

¹⁰ Scottish Government. (2019) Best Start Grant. Online from <https://www.mygov.scot/best-start-grant/>

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¹³ Scottish Government. (2018) Tackling childhood obesity. Online from <https://news.gov.scot/news/tackling-childhood-obesity>

¹⁴ Scottish Government. (2018) Climate Change Plan: third report on proposals and policies – written statement. Online from <https://www.gov.scot/publications/climate-change-plan-third-report-proposals-policies-written-statement-9781788516778/pages/25/>

Ensure healthy lives and promote well-being for all at all ages

Community Health Exchange

The Community Health Exchange (CHEX) has been part of the Scottish Community Development Centre (SCDC) since 1999 and works to support and promote community development approaches to improve health and wellbeing. We provide support to a network of community-led health initiatives and their public sector partners who are tackling health inequalities in communities across Scotland. We work strategically to support community-led health initiatives to engage with policy makers, and operationally to help link community-led health initiatives, voluntary organisations, and public sector agencies together to tackle health inequalities and achieve health and wellbeing outcomes with and within their communities.

How is Scotland doing against this Goal?

Over recent decades, life expectancy has risen and we have seen improvements in people's health in Scotland not only because of universal health care provision, but also due to improvements in the things that keep us healthy – access to housing, education, employment, social support, income, and community support. However, not everybody has benefited from these improvements. Since 2012, the decline in mortality has stalled across the whole population of Scotland and has actually risen in the most socioeconomically deprived areas.¹ This can be explained by the existence of health inequalities, defined as the unfair and avoidable differences in people's health across social groups and between different population groups. They result in thousands of unnecessary premature deaths every year. Men in Scotland's most deprived areas spend nearly 24 fewer years in 'good health'. This is unfair because these health inequalities do not occur randomly but are socially determined by circumstances largely beyond an individual's control.² In Edinburgh, for example, despite being only two miles apart, the gap in average life expectancy at birth between those living in the residential neighbourhoods near to the Bankhead tramline stop compared to those living near the Balgreen tramline stop is almost 11 years for men and 8 years for women.³

Those living in poverty and/or who are marginalised will continue to experience poorer health than other groups unless there is a significant effort to reduce the inequalities that persist in Scotland. From a community development perspective, there are many examples of local community-led initiatives that focus on supporting those most in need to improve their health and wellbeing. However well this work achieves positive health outcomes for local people, this will arguably only serve to mitigate the worst effects of poverty and austerity unless there is action at all levels to re-address imbalances in power, income and wealth.

Local councils have experienced a real terms funding cut of 9.6% over the last eight years with increasing demand for services, particularly from a growing older population.⁴ The continuous reduction in public funding makes it increasingly difficult for good statutory service provision and particularly difficult for organisations in our sector to tackle 'coal face inequalities' in the communities where they are most likely to occur.

Is Scotland committed to achieving this Goal?

The legislative and policy context for health improvements and for reducing health inequalities in Scotland is strong. 'Creating a healthier Scotland' is one of the five key objectives in the Scottish Government's National Performance Framework, with two of the sixteen Strategic Objectives being 'We live longer, healthier lives' and 'We have tackled the significant inequalities in Scottish society'.

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A series of national strategies for mental health, alcohol, diet and obesity, and maternal and infant nutrition are now in place, and the Health and Social Care Delivery Plan from December 2016 has supported action to develop six national priorities for public health as well as the creation of a single public health body for Scotland in 2020. These policies are augmented across other policy areas which focus on tackling the wider social determinants of health.

However, there is widespread acknowledgement that progress to implement these policies and strategies is slow, and that they are not yet achieving the intended impact to reduce inequalities and improve health particularly for those who experience the poorest health and social outcomes. This is exacerbated by many years of austerity and welfare reform which have resulted in significant cuts to all public services and a reduction in the workforce that delivers services across sectors, all of which have hit the poorest hardest. In sum, whilst Scottish health policy is strong on principle, more needs to be done to speed up implementation to achieve the policy aspirations to reduce health inequalities.

What should Scotland do better to achieve this Goal?

There is increasing recognition that whilst access to health services is important at times when people are ill, good health and well-being goes far beyond the control of the NHS. Health is the business of everyone, and there needs to be a shift towards preventing people getting ill in the first place and towards helping people to live in good health. This requires a focus on addressing the wider determinants of health. A shift in investment towards preventative, self-help, and peer-led approaches to tackling health issues is imperative if we are to gain ground in improving Scotland's health. There is mounting evidence that unless people feel in control of their health and their lives, and unless power imbalances are redressed, there will be little room for further improvement.

The reform of Public Health Scotland is a move into the right direction, with the new six public health priorities set to tackle the wider determinants of health and a call for leadership across all sectors to adopt a whole-system-approach to change. If successful, this prioritisation should ultimately lead to a shift in the balance of power and resources to better address community needs and issues. The reform of Public Health Scotland will require a health-in-all-policies approach, a shared evidence base on what works, and a focus on mobilising the workforce from all sectors to tackle inequalities.

Lastly, communities themselves have a critical role to play in the process to shift the balance of power and we should support people to identify what affects their health to enable co-produced solutions to take effect.

Case study — community-led health organisations

Community-led health organisations are typically rooted in the communities where they work to a social model of health. They provide a range of services to meet local people's needs, help them to identify issues that affect their health, and support them to take individual and collective action on these issues. Although they can evidence achievement of positive health and social outcomes for people in their own communities, it can be difficult to gauge their aggregated impact on health, largely because they are so diverse and because of the difficulty in measuring this.

Edinburgh Community Health Forum comprises a range of community health initiatives who deliver services and support to people experiencing the poorest health and social

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outcomes. The Forum worked with local authority staff administering Edinburgh’s Inequalities Fund to create an evaluation model that would allow individual projects to show a collective impact on the health of local people and meet the priorities of local health agencies. The table below shows the impact of 36 projects on various aspects of health.

This is important because community-led organisations often report they feel undervalued and say they experience little recognition for the impact they have on health outcomes, especially when compared to local NHS or local authority departments with large budgets and resultant greater capacity to achieve population-level outcomes. This evaluation model shows that, by aggregating data from a range of community-led organisations, that these organisations have a significant impact on thousands of individuals, often those who are most marginalised and those who public agencies struggle to reach. The data therefore suggests that a shift in resources to invest in community-led health approaches/ organisations would have a greater capacity to achieve policy aspirations than the current practice of concentrating the vast majority of resources on the delivery of health services.

Further reading

- Scottish Public Health Observatory: www.scotpho.org.uk
- NHS Health Scotland: www.healthscotland.scot
- Community Health Exchange: www.chex.org.uk
- Voluntary Health Scotland: www.vhscotland.org.uk
- Scottish Health Council – scottishhealthcouncil.org

Author

Susan Paxton, Head of Programmes at the Scottish Community Development Centre

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Ensure healthy lives and promote well-being for all at all ages

ALLIANCE
HEALTH AND SOCIAL CARE
ALLIANCE SCOTLAND
people at the centre

Health and Social Care Alliance Scotland

The Health and Social Care Alliance Scotland (the ALLIANCE) is the national third sector intermediary for health and social care with a growing and diverse membership. It includes more than 2,800 large national support providers, small local volunteer-led groups, people who are disabled, living with long-term conditions or providing unpaid care, and professionals. Our vision is for a Scotland where people of all ages who are disabled or living with long-term conditions, and unpaid carers, have a strong voice and enjoy their right to live well, as equal and active citizens, free from discrimination, with support and services that put them at the centre.

How is Scotland doing against this Goal?

Progress against some Goal 3 Targets and Indicators – for example, maternal and infant mortality – is good; however, health inequalities persist. Scotland continues to have the highest rates of premature death for men and women in Britain, and the latest estimates indicate that the increase in life expectancy has stalled.¹ In the more affluent areas of Scotland, women experience over 22 more years of good health and men experience over 23 more years compared to the most deprived areas. In 2017, suicide in young men increased for the third consecutive year,² and drug-related deaths in Scotland have more than doubled in 10 years.³ Specific groups in society continue to experience worse health outcomes than others. For example, there are ongoing problems with timely diagnosis of conditions such as endometriosis. This means many women experience prolonged periods of pain and distress and allows the condition to progress and become more difficult to treat.⁴ One area for further exploration would be the extent to which data gaps and bias impact on women’s and girls’ health in Scotland. This exploration should go beyond their reproductive and maternal health which has been the predominant focus of healthcare initiatives targeting women. NHS Health Scotland notes that life expectancy for people with learning disabilities is shorter compared to the general population, often due to avoidable, preventable and manageable conditions.⁵ Life expectancy for women with a diagnosis of schizophrenia is 15 years less than the general population, and for men it is 20 years less.⁶ Despite the duty to carry out Equality Impact Assessments (EIAs), other seldom-heard groups continue to be disproportionately impacted by poor health and wellbeing outcomes. This includes disabled people, older people, members of the BME community, members of the Gypsy/Traveller and Roma communities, people who identify as LGBT+ and care experienced (young) people, amongst others.

Is Scotland committed to achieving this Goal?

There appears to be a high level of policy commitment to achieving good health and wellbeing in Scotland, with health and social care making up a substantial proportion of the national budget. The National Performance Framework (NPF) contains a National Outcome – ‘We are healthy and active’ – with nine associated Indicators. Successive Programmes for Government⁷ have committed to a wide range of health and wellbeing initiatives, most recently targeting specific population groups (e.g. children and young people) and service sectors (e.g. primary/acute/secondary care). The 2016 Health and Social Care Delivery Plan was published to ‘up the pace of improvement and change within Scotland’s health and care system’. The Chief Medical Officer’s annual report, *Realistic Medicine*,⁸ consistently encourages health professionals to commit to a more personalised approach, and Scotland’s human rights-based Health and Social Care Standards set out what people can expect when using health, social care or social work services in Scotland. The ongoing processes to integrate health and social care and imbue social care with choice and control for people accessing support are both underpinned by legislation. Other policies focus

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on achieving positive impacts in a diverse range of areas, such as dementia, cancer, free personal care, digital health and care, Getting it Right for Every Child (GIRFEC), Adverse Childhood Experiences (ACES), and more. What is less clear, however, is whether people's health, wellbeing and experiences are consistently improving as a result of this wealth of policy. Regulatory bodies, including Audit Scotland and the Care Inspectorate, report persistent problems in achieving policy goals (the 'implementation gap'). It is also unclear whether small scale improvement programmes to existing models that are underway around the country will result in the larger paradigm shift that is required to achieve positive change at a population level. In the meantime, people continue to experience obstacles to fully realising their right to health and accessing the right support at the right time. For example, people experiencing mental ill-health lack adequate access to prevention and early intervention measures which would help mitigate against greater crises in later life. Elsewhere, people are unnecessarily stuck in hospital, unable to be discharged and return home because timely social care support is not put in place.

What should Scotland do better to achieve this Goal?

There is a role for everyone to play in helping to achieve Goal 3, including the public, private and third sectors, people who access services and support, and wider civil society. Many of the solutions to Scotland's seemingly intractable health and wellbeing problems cannot be achieved by the health and social care sector alone. They require joined-up working and cross-sectoral approaches that focus on the underlying determinants of health and inequalities in Scottish people's income, wealth and power.

Health and social care are high profile and often contentious issues in Scottish politics. Nationally and locally the narrative must be reframed so that strategic decision-making and action is based on evidence and outcomes rather than (short-term) political goals and reactive responses. Politicians across all parties and public sector officials could demonstrate substantial leadership here.

National and local government and health and social care agencies should involve third sector organisations, communities and people in free, meaningful and active decision-making – this is fundamental to achieving good health and wellbeing across Scotland. Other goals should be to:

- Review and improve existing policy and address the implementation gaps (e.g. Self-directed Support; mental health legislation; health and social care integration).
- Make a meaningful shift in resources, as well as in language, towards prevention and early intervention.
- Take an explicitly rights-based approach in practice as well as in policy (e.g. apply the AAAQ and PANEL Principle frameworks⁹).
- Explore alternative ways of overcoming fiscal obstacles (e.g. Human Rights Budget Work).
- Future proof the health and social care workforce (e.g. improve pay and conditions).

Further reading

- Health and Social Care Alliance Scotland (the ALLIANCE): <https://www.alliance-scotland.org.uk/>
- Scottish Government, Health and Social Care: <https://www.gov.scot/health-and-social-care/>
- CoSLA, Health and Social Care: <http://www.cosla.gov.uk/about-cosla/how-we-are->

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- Health and Social Care Scotland: <https://hscscotland.scot/>
- NHS Health Scotland: <http://www.healthscotland.scot/>
- Audit Scotland: <http://www.audit-scotland.gov.uk/>
- Care Inspectorate: <http://www.careinspectorate.com/>
- Scottish Public Health Network: <https://www.scotphn.net/>
- Engender: Disabled Women – Our Bodies, Our Rights: <https://www.engender.org.uk/files/our-bodies,-our-rights-identifying-and-removing-barriers-to-disabled-womens-reproductive-rights-in-scotland.pdf>
- Concluding observations on the initial report of the United Kingdom of Great Britain and Northern Ireland - Alternative report from civil society: <https://inclusionscotland.org/wp-content/uploads/2018/10/Final-DDPO-UNCRPD-alternative-12-month-follow-up-report-2018-.doc>
- Scottish Human Rights Commission: Getting it Right? An Overview of Human Rights in Scotland: <http://www.snaprights.info/how-snap-was-developed/getting-it-right>

Author

Lucy Mulvagh, Director of Policy and Communications, supported by the ALLIANCE team.

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⁷Scottish Government. (2018) Programme for Government. Online from <https://www.gov.scot/programme-for-government/>

⁸Realistic Medicine. (2019) Chief Medical Officer. Online from <https://www.realisticmedicine.scot/>

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Ensure inclusive and equitable quality education and promote lifelong learning opportunities for all

International Development Education Association Scotland

Global Citizenship Education (GCE) is an active learning process that builds critical understanding of the economic, social, political and environmental forces that shape our lives. It supports the development of skills, attitudes and values that enable people to contribute to the development of a more just and sustainable world, in which power and resources are more equitably shared. IDEAS, the International Development Education Association Scotland, is the national network for civil society organisations involved in delivery, advocacy and development of Global Citizenship Education. Members include large NGOs, small organisations, and individuals as well as the regionally based Development Education Centres (DECs) who provide local practical support. By raising awareness of global interdependencies and illustrating the potential for change, the IDEAS network aims to influence those involved in all sectors of formal and informal education and lifelong learning.

How is Scotland doing against this Goal?

Global Citizenship Education (GCE) lies at the heart of Goal Target 4.7 and the drive towards sustainable development. We value the Scottish Government's commitment to GCE within formal education, which predates the SDGs. GCE is embedded as a cross-cutting theme in the national Curriculum for Excellence (CfE). Learning for Sustainability (an umbrella term covering GCE, Sustainable Development Education and Outdoor Learning) is an entitlement for all pupils and one of three core priorities within the General Teaching Council Scotland's Professional Standards. The sustained and collaborative approach of the organisations within the IDEAS network has been crucial to creating this world-leading GCE policy context. For over 20 years, IDEAS has worked in partnership with statutory stakeholders – the Scottish Government, Education Scotland, and the General Teaching Council Scotland – to embed Global Citizenship Education in practice, from early years through to university-based teacher education programmes, using funding secured at Scottish, UK and European levels. This has included working with academics in order to develop research and support evidence-based policy-making in this area.

IDEAS values the positive policy context within which we operate in Scotland as this supports and underpins the quality implementation of GCE within schools. However, while the primary school sector often excels in delivering GCE, the secondary school sector is often hampered by the dissonance between Scottish Qualification Authority's (SQA) exam requirements and the more creative and learner-led approaches espoused by GCE. Furthermore, it is important to recognise the role Global Citizenship Education can play in delivery across all SDGs, rather than Goal 4 in isolation. It is a proven approach to empowering people of all ages to critically consider the global social and environmental issues underpinning the SDGs, and what can be done to achieve them. In Scotland, there is a significant lack of awareness of the SDGs, even within the many organisations and sectors that share their values and ambitions. SDG implementation and planning would be improved by including GCE approaches in the development of public awareness, civic action and cross-government engagement with the SDGs.

Is Scotland committed to achieving this Goal?

The Scottish Government's strategic policy commitment to GCE in formal education is among the strongest in Europe. This policy commitment is evident in the Government's contribution to the core funding of the Development Education Centres. This support has sustained and enhanced the development and delivery of sector expertise in Scotland, enabling the DECs to draw in very significant additional funding from the UK Government

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and via the European Commission's Development Education and Awareness Raising fund (DEAR). The Scottish Government's core funding to DEC's is becoming ever more crucial with significant cuts to GCE funding from the UK's Department for International Development and the likely loss of access to the European Commission's DEAR fund in the wake of Brexit. Current education policy prioritises the closing of the poverty-related attainment gap. This is frequently interpreted through a narrow focus on literacy and numeracy and an increased emphasis on testing. We argue that social justice lies at the heart of both closing the attainment gap and GCE. Therefore, it is vital that they are understood as mutually enhancing, not competing. We hope that the Learning for Sustainability Action Plan¹ will set out a well-resourced and clear direction for education stakeholders so that the policy commitment can be fully implemented. The Scottish Government is currently working with IDEAS² on GCE as a key area under its developing commitment to Policy Coherence for Sustainable Development (PCSD).³ We are not aware of any other examples globally of GCE being highlighted within PCSD in this way. This work will build a stronger context for delivery of Goal Target 4.7, and all the Goals, in Scotland by:

- developing approaches to measuring national progress in education that reflect all four Curriculum for Excellence capacities and the contribution of GCE to delivering them;
- exploring the role GCE can play in supporting cross-government work on understanding the SDGs and embedding them in policy-making processes;
- developing alignment between education policy and addressing poverty in Scotland by exploring synergies with approaches to tackling poverty internationally.

What should Scotland do better to achieve this Goal?

The core requirements in Scotland over the coming years are strategic and budgetary support to ensure the implementation and delivery of the strong policy commitment to Goal Target 4.7 within formal education, especially in the face of diminished UK level funding and the prospect of exclusion from European funding. The forthcoming Learning for Sustainability Action Plan must drive change that delivers the full potential of the Scottish Government's policy commitment. As noted, GCE and Learning for Sustainability are widely understood as being complementary to closing the attainment gap. The joining-up of these agendas has resonance under the totality of SDG 4, contributing to quality education that tackles inequality by focusing on the whole child,⁴ rather than through a narrow assessment-led approach. In IDEAS' 'Understanding the Impact of Global Citizenship Education – a Theory of Change Approach' report we argue that a shared focus on pupil voice and pupil engagement is key in addressing disadvantage⁵ and providing an education that prepares children and young people for the increasingly urgent challenges of our world; one in which sources of information are increasingly contested.

While education policy is devolved to the Scottish Parliament, Brexit presents a specific challenge to Scotland's delivery of Goal Target 4.7. Scottish education has long sustained strong links with schools, educators, delivery partners and processes⁶ within the European Union, including through participation in the European Commission's Development Education and Awareness Raising (DEAR) stream⁷ and Erasmus +. These links and collaborative partnerships, which also encompass wider global processes, must be protected, especially with regard to progressing the SDGs. Statutory stakeholders, including the Scottish Government, along with civil society must take shared action in this regard, including though the opportunities currently offered by IDEAS' Bridge 47 project.⁸

Ensure inclusive and equitable quality education and promote lifelong learning opportunities for all

Case study — embedding the SDGs in school curricula

Fenwick Primary school's engagement with UNICEF's Rights Respecting Schools Award programme has provided inspiration for an ambitious 5-year plan to embed the SDGs across the whole school curriculum. The Kilmarnock school started its 'rights journey' in February 2018 and quickly progressed to achieving the Silver Award. It became clear to the school, that the rights of a child made direct correlations to the SDGs and to Vision2030+ which calls for a coherent, whole school approach to Learning for Sustainability. The pupils themselves were very motivated by the work and keen to ensure that they were playing their part in sustaining the world for themselves and future generations.

Following on from the success of embedding a rights respecting approach into the school's ethos and into assemblies focussed on global issues, the pupils began exploring and questioning the world around them. The teaching staff team decided to investigate the SDGs in more depth and to work to ensure that they are embedded within the curriculum. After introducing the SDGs to all staff at a development evening staff set about creating a 5-year plan. They looked for connections and links across the SDGs and 'bundled' those which cover similar topics together. The next step was to review the current curriculum content and identify opportunities for delivering these SDG 'bundles' over five years. To date, all classes have been introduced to the SDGs and all have completed their World's Largest Lesson and received a participation certificate. All teachers have incorporated the 5-year SDG planner into their forward planning and started to identify further opportunities for raising awareness about the SDGs in the local community.

Pupils are already raising the profile of SDGs by initiating and supporting local initiatives such as providing donations to the local foodbank and participating in a local litter pick and 'dog mess' campaign. The pupils at Fenwick primary school are keen to share their learning around the SDGs with their parents, carers, friends, and family. The school's long-term planning will ensure they have the skills and knowledge to do this effectively.

Further reading

- IDEAS <http://www.ideas-forum.org.uk/> is Scotland's civil society Global Citizenship Education network whose members deliver projects, resources and expertise that deliver on SDG 4.7 and support the development of public understanding of all the SDGs, especially among educators of children and young people.
- Scotland's Development Education Centres <http://www.ideas-forum.org.uk/about-us/decs> provide a wide variety of local face-to-face professional development opportunities for educators around global citizenship education and the SDGs. They cover all Local Authority areas from their bases in Aberdeen, Dundee, Edinburgh, Glasgow and Inverness.
- Scotdec provides a wide range of GCE resources for schools including specific materials for teaching children and young people about the SDGs www.scotdec.org.uk/resources.
- Stride magazine <http://www.stridemagazine.org.uk/> and Signposts <http://www.signpostsglobalcitizenship.org/> provide features, activities and resources for educators engaging with the SDGs
- Connecting Classrooms through Global Learning is a British Council/DFID funded programme providing opportunities for teachers and schools to engage with the SDGs <http://www.ideas-forum.org.uk/education/schools/projects/connecting-classrooms-through-global-learning>
- Measuring impact and progress in global citizenship education is challenging as it is

Ensure inclusive and equitable quality education and promote lifelong learning opportunities for all

focused on values and attitudes as well as complex skills such as critical thinking. This report addresses these challenges using a Theory of Change approach [http://www.ideas-forum.org.uk/images/education/IDEAS-impact-report-\(for-web\).pdf](http://www.ideas-forum.org.uk/images/education/IDEAS-impact-report-(for-web).pdf).

- Bridge 47 <http://www.ideas-forum.org.uk/education/schools/projects/bridge-47> is an international European Commission funded project driving action on the Global Citizenship Education Goal - SDG 4.7 - and building recognition that this approach to education supports delivery of all the SDGs, as well as being a Goal in its own right. IDEAS is the Scottish partner on this project which is led by the Finnish International Development civil society platform, FINGO.

Authors

Tanya Wisely, Global Citizenship Education advisor at Oxfam, and Charlotte Dwyer, Director of Scotdec – on behalf of IDEAS

¹The Vision 2030+ Action Plan is expected in Early Summer 2019. It follows on from the Scottish Government's acceptance of the One Planet Schools Ministerial Working Group's recommendations in 2013 and the Vision 2030+ report published in 2016

²The overarching work on Policy Coherence for Sustainable Development has been led by Scotland's International Development Alliance

³This aligns with the cross-governmental approach to the SDGs proposed under the National Performance Framework

⁴In line with both GIRFEC and Curriculum for Excellence

⁵See IDEAS 'Understanding the Impact of Global Citizenship Education – a Theory of Change Approach' report at [http://www.ideas-forum.org.uk/images/education/IDEAS-impact-report-\(for-web\).pdf](http://www.ideas-forum.org.uk/images/education/IDEAS-impact-report-(for-web).pdf)

⁶E.g. Concord – the European network of civil society organisations involved in International Development, the Maastricht Declaration 20xx, the European Commission's Development Education and Awareness Raising stream, the inter-governmental Global Education Network Europe (GENE), the Academic Network on Global Education and Learning (ANGEL) research network

⁷There are currently Scottish partners in four DEAR projects, all of which have a specific SDG focus.

⁸IDEAS is a leading partner in Bridge 47: Building Global Citizenship (2017-2020), a project co-created and implemented by 15 European and global civil society organisations. It focuses on advocating for Global Citizenship Education (GCE) and building GCE capacity, innovation and partnerships at national, European and global levels to ensure that SDG 4.7 is delivered.

Achieve gender equality and empower all women and girls

Girlguiding Scotland

Girlguiding Scotland is the leading charity for girls and young women in Scotland, with around 50,000 young members. We build girls' confidence and raise their aspirations. We give them the chance to discover their full potential and encourage them to be a powerful force for good. Through our work we inspire and equip girls to be confident and resilient in an ever-changing world, and provide a safe, supportive and non-judgmental environment for girls as they grow up.

How is Scotland doing against this Goal?

Girlguiding Scotland believes the Scottish Government has, overall, made good progress towards achieving SDG 5, namely in relation to establishing legal frameworks aimed at ending gender-based discrimination and gender-based violence. There are, however, areas that require further work, largely centred around the full and effective participation of women and equal opportunities for leadership at all levels of decision-making in political, economic and public life and access to sexual and reproductive health services and information. This assessment is made on the basis of findings from our own research in relation to SDG 5 Targets and Indicators. If this SDG is not achieved it will be the next generation of young women who will be most affected when entering the labour market. They could continue to be subject to gender stereotyping, discrimination and lack of opportunity; they could continue to experience disproportionate levels of violence and live in a society where women are not represented or have the same opportunities as men. The table below sets out Girlguiding Scotland's assessment of progress with regards to selected SDG 5 Targets and Indicators. Green indicates good progress, orange indicates some progress and red indicates lack of progress. Only targets relevant to the data available to Girlguiding Scotland are included.

Achieve gender equality and empower all women and girls

Targets	Indicators	Progress	Comments
5.1 End all forms of discrimination against all women and girls everywhere.	5.1.1 Whether or not legal frameworks are in place to promote, enforce and monitor equality and non discrimination based on sex.		<p>Gender Pay Gap We are pleased to note the gender pay gap for full-time employees has decreased, from 10.8% in 2008 to 5.7% in 2018. Overall, Scotland's gender pay gap is below the UK-wide gap of 8.6% (2018). While this decrease is a positive sign, the gap should not exist at all. We therefore welcome the Scottish Government's Gender Pay Gap Action Plan to help meet its commitment of reducing the gender pay gap by 2021 – including investing an extra £5 million over the next three years to support around 2,000 women to return to work after career breaks, and the requirement on public authorities with more than 20 employees to publish their pay gap every two years and an equal pay statement every four years.</p> <p>Workplace Equality Fund We welcomed the announcement that this will be expanded for 2019/20 to allow the Scottish Government to reach more employers to make the necessary changes to ensure equality in their workplaces.</p> <p>Scottish Business Pledge We note the introduction of the Scottish Business Pledge in 2015 and the commitment in 2018 by Scottish Ministers to carry out a short review to make the Pledge more attractive to business, improve uptake and impact, including a refresh of the gender and diversity element of Pledge which we believe is necessary in light of the Gender Pay Gap Action Plan.</p> <p>Gender Representation We found 62% of girls would like to be a leader in their chosen job, but 45% said they thought this would be harder because they are female. The introduction of the Gender Representation on Public Boards (Scotland) Bill – which aims to ensure that women make up at least 50% of non-executive board members – is a welcome move to place statutory obligations on appointees to consider gender balance. We further note the Partnership for Change, a voluntary commitment for gender balance on boards across all sectors of 50/50 by 2020. We would, however, like to see the Partnership for Change be placed on a statutory basis.</p> <p>National Advisory Council on Women and Girls (NACWG) Girlguiding Scotland is please to participate in the First Minister's NACWG which exists to advise the First Minister on what is needed to tackle gender inequality in Scotland. We believe this approach to use experts and leaders in the field to advise the Scottish Government on what action to take to achieve cultural change in Scotland that is needed to advance gender equality to be important and effective.</p>

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Targets	Indicators	Progress	Comments
5.2 Eliminate all forms of violence against all women and girls in the public and private spheres, including trafficking and sexual and other types of exploitation.	<p>5.2.1 Proportion of ever-partnered women and girls aged 15 years and older subjected to physical, sexual or psychological violence by a current or former intimate partner in the previous 12 months, by form of violence and by age.</p> <p>5.2.2 Proportion of women and girls aged 15 years and older subjected to sexual violence by persons other than an intimate partner in the previous 12 months, by age and place of occurrence.</p>	●	<p>Our Girls in Scotland Survey 2018 found the following percentages of girls who know another girl their age (13-25) who has experienced the following:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 43% controlling behaviour or bullying from a partner • 37% rape or sexual assault • 33% violence from partner • 22% threatened with sexual violence <p>These results demonstrate physical, sexual or psychological violence are continuing to affect high numbers of girls and young women in Scotland.</p> <p>Sexual Harassment in Schools We have called on the Scottish Government to take urgent action on the widespread, but often hidden, issue of sexual harassment in schools. We are pleased the Scottish Government has acted to better record such incidents. While we welcome this step, we believe there is still more to be done to ensure every girl feels safe and happy at school.</p> <p>Equally Safe We note that 'Equally Safe: Scotland's Strategy to Eradicate Violence Against Women' has been updated since 2014 with a focus on prioritising prevention of violence against women and girls. We believe this update is important and welcome the fact that further stakeholder engagement has taken place to ensure that issues relating to children and young people are given due attention.</p> <p>Domestic Abuse (Scotland) Bill We note that in April 2019 this Bill came into force which created a statutory offence of domestic abuse against a partner or ex-partner. We also welcome the fact that this includes not only physical abuse, but psychological and emotional treatment and coercive and controlling behaviour. We agree with the Scottish Government, Police Scotland, and other charities that this legislation is ground-breaking and believe it sends a positive message that Scotland is taking meaningful action to end all forms of violence against all women and girls in the public and private spheres.</p>
5.5 Ensure women's full and effective participation and equal opportunities for leadership at all levels of decision-making in political, economic and public life.	<p>5.5.1 Proportion of seats held by women in national parliaments and local governments</p> <p>5.5.2 Proportion of women in managerial positions.</p>	●	<p>While we welcome the First Minister's commitment to a gender-balanced cabinet, we note only 35% of MSPs are women. Moreover, no party stood an equal number of women to men as candidates, and one party stood no women candidates for the 2016 election. At local government level, only 29% of elected councillors in 2017 were women, up only 4% from 24% in 2012. Looking at the upcoming European Parliament elections there has been some improvement, with over half of the parties standing candidates in Scotland putting forward 50:50 lists (excluding independent candidates). Girlguiding Scotland partnered with Women 50:50 to launch a new campaign called Citizen Girl. This campaign made calls on political parties to commit to gender equality by putting forward 50% female candidates in local, Scottish and UK elections and to have this requirement made on a statutory basis. We are pleased to see key figures in Scottish politics support this call, notably the First Minister. There is also support from elected representatives from across nearly all key political parties in Scotland, with the exception of one. Citizen Girl also called on businesses, public bodies, and voluntary organisations in Scotland to commit to increasing female representation in management. While there has been some improvement in the representation of women in politics and initiatives, further work is required.</p>

Achieve gender equality and empower all women and girls

Targets	Indicators	Progress	Comments
5.6 Ensure universal access to sexual and reproductive health and reproductive rights as agreed in accordance with the Programme of Action of the International Conference on Population and Development and the Beijing Platform for Action and the outcome documents of their review conferences.	5.6.1 Proportion of women aged 15–49 years who make their own informed decisions regarding sexual relations, contraceptive use and reproductive health care. 5.6.2 Number of countries with laws and regulations that guarantee women aged 15–49 years access to sexual and reproductive health care, information and education.		<p>Our Girls in Scotland 2018 survey gathered significant data concerning girls' views (aged 13–25) on sex education. Notably, 37% of girls aged 13–25 said they felt uncomfortable talking with a trusted adult about sex and pregnancy; 78% said they learnt little or nothing about consent; 84% said they learnt little or nothing about sexual harassment and abuse; 90% said they learnt little or nothing about online pornography; 78% said they learnt little or nothing about healthy relationships; and 84% said they learnt little or nothing about gender equality.</p> <p>Of additional concern is that while Health Boards are legally required to support women to access abortion services up until 24 weeks' gestation, many local health boards have a lower gestational time limit, the lowest being 15 weeks and 5 days. It is unclear as to the reasoning for this and how women beyond the local health board time limit will access abortion services.</p> <p>Girlguiding Scotland is also campaigning to end period poverty in Scotland and welcome the Member's Bill that would introduce a universal system for provision of sanitary products and create a duty for schools, colleges and universities to provide free sanitary products in toilets. We also welcome the decision by the Scottish Government to provide free sanitary products at schools, colleges, universities, libraries and leisure centres across Scotland. We note this is not a statutory basis.</p>

Is Scotland committed to achieving this Goal?

We believe the Scottish Government has demonstrated a strong commitment to achieve SDG 5 through legislation and policy and we are pleased to see gender equality being prioritised. While many of the initiatives may not produce immediate results, we believe they constitute an important initial step in challenging and changing attitudes surrounding gender equality. We are particularly pleased to see an increase in legal frameworks aimed at ending gender discrimination, as well as the establishment of the NACWG, drawing on expertise to influence and shape policy surrounding gender equality.

To attain SDG 5, there is a need to have initiatives aimed at changing societal attitudes alongside legislative action aimed at reducing gender equality. A good example of this is the Scottish Government's awareness-raising campaign to improve public understanding of what constitutes domestic abuse under the new Domestic Abuse (Scotland) Act. It should also be recognised that, as many of the policies and key pieces of legislation are in their infancy, the full impact of these are yet to be seen and will require further monitoring and data analysis.

What should Scotland do better to achieve this Goal?

Further work is needed involving all sectors, including central and local governments, the private sector and the third sector working together and listening to each other. There are various policy calls we continue to make on the Scottish Government and on other sectors. These include, but are not limited to, the following:

- National guidance to ensure schools know how to take a zero-tolerance approach to sexual harassment;
- More focus in school on teaching about gender equality – including more women represented in school subjects;
- A statutory duty on political parties to stand at least 50% women candidates;

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- More businesses to commit to the Partnership for Change and the Scottish Business Pledge;
- Action to implement the recommendations made following the review of Personal and Social Education in Scotland.

There is also the need to change attitudes about women, including an end to stereotypes that can consequentially lead to girls and women being treated differently or impacted negatively because of their gender. This will only be achieved through education, an increase in the representation of women and women's voices in public life and in positions of leadership.

Case study — seeking evidence on gender equality

The establishment of the National Advisory Council on Women and Girls (NACWG) is an extremely valuable asset for Scotland, and Girlguiding Scotland are pleased to participate in this. This Council – independent of government – is in a unique position to seek the views and evidence from all stakeholders across Scotland, using this to form recommendations to the First Minister on how to achieve gender equality. We look forward to continuing to participate in the Council and adding our expertise and views on how to achieve gender equality in Scotland.

Further reading

- The Girls in Scotland Survey 2018: <https://www.girlguidingscotland.org.uk/wp-content/uploads/2018/11/Girls-in-Scotland-survey-2018-compressed.pdf>
- Future Girl: <https://www.girlguiding.org.uk/girls-making-change/future-girl/>

Author

Nicoletta Primo, Public Relations and Policy Officer at Girlguiding Scotland

Ensure availability and sustainable management of water and sanitation for all

Citizens Advice Scotland

Citizens Advice Scotland (CAS), our 59-member Citizen Advice Bureaux (CAB), and the Extra Help Unit form Scotland's largest independent advice network. Advice provided by our service is free, independent, confidential, impartial and available to everyone.

As well as providing advice, CAS uses research and evidence to put consumers at the heart of policy and regulation in the water sector in Scotland. We work with government, regulators and business to put consumers first, designing policy and practice around their needs and aspirations. This includes working with water industry stakeholders to support the development of policy around private water and wastewater services.

How is Scotland doing against this Goal?

CAS is pleased with the progress Scotland is making against SDG 6. In 2017/18, Scottish Water, the public supplier of water and wastewater services to most households in Scotland, had fewer Environmental Pollution Incidents than in any previous year. Scottish Water and the Scottish Environmental Protection Agency (SEPA) are working in partnership to improve the quality of bathing waters in Scotland. In 2017, 86% of bathing water met the minimum EU Bathing Water Directive standards. Scottish Water is currently conducting research into consumer priorities around the environment to inform future policy around reducing pollution.¹ The Scottish water industry recognises the essential role consumers play in achieving SDG 6. Scottish Water, working in partnership with the Energy Saving Trust, has provided water efficiency advice to 49,000 homes in priority areas across Scotland.² Through social media and television campaigns, Scottish Water encourages consumers to reduce water wastage and to dispose of household waste (e.g. fats, oils, grease, and wet wipes) correctly in order to protect the environment. CAS welcomes Scottish Water's work on educating consumers in order to support the achievement of Goal Targets 6.4 and 6.6. Households in Scotland using the public supply have access to a safe and continuous supply of drinking water. Scottish Water has a robust programme of investment to ensure the water network can provide for Scotland's geographically diverse population, and in 2017 water quality achieved 99.91% compliance with the EU Drinking Water Directive.³ Scottish Water also responds quickly when there are interruptions to services to ensure households are provided with alternative water supplies.

However, there is still progress to be made in Scotland towards fully attaining Goal Target 6.1 – to 'achieve universal and equitable access to safe and affordable drinking water for all' by 2030. Around 180,000 people in Scotland receive their drinking water from private water supplies rather than from the public network. Many private water supplies are not treated or are treated inadequately, which can place those using the supply at risk of health issues. For example, in 2017, the Drinking Water Quality Regulator found traces of E. Coli in 12% of unregulated private water supplies.⁴ Additionally, many consumers using private water supplies are not guaranteed a continuous water supply. During the 2018 summer drought many private water supplies (wells, springs, boreholes) ran out of water, and household reliant on these supplies required emergency intervention from the Scottish Government and local authorities.

Is Scotland committed to achieving this Goal?

CAS believes that the Scottish Government, as well as other water industry stakeholders, are committed to achieving SDG 6. The Scottish Government is currently developing the Principles of Charging and Ministerial Objectives for the 2021-2027 regulatory period and is consulting on a number of policy areas which will contribute towards achieving this Goal, such as ensuring that Scotland maintains compliance with drinking water quality standards.

Ensure availability and sustainable management of water and sanitation for all

As part of their draft Strategic Plan for the 2021-2027 regulatory period, Scottish Water have committed to SDG 6 through their promise to deliver a consistently leading customer experience; increase reliability and resilience; support a flourishing Scotland; and treat customers' money with respect.⁶ CAS has welcomed Scottish Water's draft Strategic Plan and believes that it clearly sets out Scottish Water's aspirations which can be built upon. CAS has encouraged Scottish Water to consider how it can further develop consumer-focused strategic outcomes within the Plan, which would support Scottish Water's commitment to establishing and delivering against a set of customer-based principles. CAS welcomes the commitment demonstrated by water industry stakeholders to keep consumers at the heart of water policy and practice, as consumer engagement and input is critical to achieving the SDG 6.

What should Scotland do better to achieve this Goal?

Water industry stakeholders have committed to working collaboratively to develop an industry vision for the 2021-2027 regulatory period. CAS welcomes this spirit of co-creation as it has generated more opportunities to work with stakeholders to identify and develop consumer-focussed outcomes. CAS believes that including consumers within the decision-making process, as well as encouraging and supporting them to change their behaviour to better protect infrastructure and the environment, is essential for the water industry to meet SDG 6. CAS believes that consumers need to be helped to better understand how their decisions can make a difference. Here, targeted messaging and education are necessary. Educating consumers on water efficiency and the need to waste less water will strengthen their understanding of how to more responsibly use natural resources and encourage them to take the right actions to conserve water. CAS also believes that to achieve SDG 6, the industry needs to consider ways of supporting 'life-wide learning'. This will take a longer-term approach to educating and influencing current as well as future consumers to change their behaviours around using public water and wastewater services. Further progress is required to achieve Goal Target 6.1 – to 'achieve universal and equitable access to safe and affordable drinking water for all'. Although water and sewerage charges are affordable for many consumers, CAS research⁷ has found that 12% of households in Scotland may struggle to afford their charges. This is a particular issue for low income households. CAS believes that services that are essential for life, such as water and sewerage, should be affordable for all consumers and that Scottish water policy needs to explore better ways of providing targeted financial support to those who need it.

Lastly, to achieve Goal Target 6.1 and ensure all consumers in Scotland, including those on private water supplies, have continuous access to safe water, the industry needs to further explore the development of a comprehensive framework of support for private water supply owners. This may involve improving access to information, training and funding to maintain their supply to a compliant standard.

Case study — community engagement

CAS fully supports Goal Target 6.B to strengthen community participation in the process of improving water management. We believe that communities are uniquely placed to work in partnership with services, providing insight into local needs and influencing the delivery of services in a way that delivers benefit for both the environment and for local communities. The Scottish water industry has committed to improving community engagement standards and Scottish Water is in the process of developing a community engagement strategy. Community engagement is an area of interest among regulated industries, yet more needs to be done to identify suitable methods of engagement; understand why

Ensure availability and sustainable management of water and sanitation for all

engaging with communities is important; and identify the principles that need to underpin good engagement within different situations. A lack of robust community engagement can result in communities feeling excluded and disengaged with what is going on in their local community. This results in a lost opportunity to find out what communities need and how partnership working could positively help to impact and protect asset health and service delivery. Additionally, consumer trust in service providers will be enhanced if communities are included and listened to, and if organisations can clearly demonstrate to communities how their input has influenced outcomes.⁸ In partnership with the Customer Forum and Scottish Water, CAS is leading on research to identify the characteristics of community engagement good practice. This work will inform Scottish Water's community engagement strategy and support the delivery of consistently high-quality engagement in policy and practice.⁹

Author

Rebecca Millar, Water Policy Officer at Citizens Advice Scotland

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² Scottish Water. (2019) ongoing research into Environment portfolio - Unpublished

³ DWQR. (2018) Drinking Water Quality 2017: Public Water Supply Report. Online from <http://dwqr.scot/media/39029/dwqr-annual-report-2017-public-water-supply.pdf>

⁴ DWQR. (2018). Drinking Water Quality in Scotland 2017: Private Water Supplies. Online from <http://dwqr.scot/media/39966/dwqr-pws-annual-report-2017-compiled-report-final-24-september-2018.pdf>

⁵ Scottish Government. (2018) Private water supplies. Online from <https://news.gov.scot/news/private-water-supplies>

⁶ Scottish Water. (2018) SR21 Outline Strategic Plan (draft)

⁷ Citizens Advice Scotland. (2018) Charting a New Course. Online from <https://www.cas.org.uk/publications/charting-new-course-study-developing-affordability-policy-water-and-sewerage-charges>

⁸ Consumer Focus Scotland. (2011) Consumer Engagement in Decision Making: Best Practice from Scottish Public Services

⁹ Citizens Advice Scotland. (2019) Ongoing research into community engagement

Ensure access to affordable, reliable, sustainable and modern energy for all

Changeworks

Changeworks is Scotland's leading environmental charity delivering solutions for low carbon living. We help people and organisations to take meaningful, urgent action to tackle climate change. For over 10 years, Changeworks have delivered the Scottish Government's Home Energy Scotland service by engaging with 33,000 householders per year in two Scottish regions, providing expert, impartial advice on energy saving, keeping warm at home, and on renewable energy. We also provide in-depth support to over 1,700 vulnerable households per year through our dedicated Affordable Warmth team, offering advice for households on energy matters.

How is Scotland doing against this Goal?

Everybody in Scotland has access to reliable energy. Yet for many, energy is not affordable. In 2017, 24.9% of households were in fuel poverty, spending more than 10% of their income on heating their home. Of these, 7% had to spend more than 20% of their income on heating, often forcing households to choose between heating and eating. Fuel poverty is much more prevalent in households who do not have access to mains gas and heat their home with electricity, oil or liquefied petroleum gas. Of the 17% of Scottish households off the gas grid, 38% are in fuel poverty.¹

Figure 1. Changeworks Fuel Poverty Map at data zone level, using data from the Scottish House Condition Survey,² the 2011 Scottish Census,³ and EPC register data

The four drivers of fuel poverty are the price of fuel, the energy efficiency of the home, low incomes, and how energy is used in the home. The Scottish Government have limited influence on the price of fuel, and low incomes are considered under other SDGs. Progress has been made to improve energy efficiency. In 2017, according to Energy Performance Certificates, 47% of Scottish homes were banded C or above. This compares to only 24% in 2010.⁵ However, the rate of improvement has slowed down. UK Government policies on energy company obligations have resulted in a decrease in the support provided by utility companies for energy efficiency measures. In contrast, the Scottish Government's Energy Efficient Scotland and Warmer Homes Scotland programmes assisted 24,000 households in 2016/17.⁶ Scotland is committed to

making energy consumption sustainable as part of its Climate Change Action Plan.

Renewable sources generated 54% of the electricity consumed in 2016, an increase from 37% over 2006,⁷ while gas remains the main form of heating. Overall, 17.8% of Scotland's total energy consumption in 2015 came from renewable sources. Energy generation and usage is changing rapidly, and the current energy systems will have to undergo significant

Ensure access to affordable, reliable, sustainable and modern energy for all

development to meet the new challenges. To ensure that all sectors of society are able to benefit from the new systems, a just transition will have to be embedded in the delivery. There are faults in the current energy system, including the lack of ease of supplier switching, incorrect billing, meter issues, and debt recovery. The demand for in-depth support is greater than what is available.

Is Scotland committed to achieving this Goal?

There is strong commitment from the Scottish Government to tackling fuel poverty and promoting clean energy. Following the recommendation of the UK Committee on Climate Change, legislation is being amended to make Scotland net-zero carbon by 2045. There is a range of policy commitments in the Scottish Government Energy Strategy which provide an integrated approach with a clear vision guided by the principles of a whole-system view, an inclusive energy transition, and a smarter local energy model. The ambition of these policies will need to be strengthened to meet the climate change commitment.

Eradicating fuel poverty is seen as being crucial to achieving a fairer, socially just, and sustainable Scotland. The Scottish Government commissioned a strategic fuel poverty review which has led to a new Fuel Poverty (Scotland) Bill being drawn up. The commitment to eradicating fuel poverty is welcome but is expected to take 20 years. The current target means that in 2040, 5% of the Scottish population will still be in fuel poverty due to poor energy efficiency. The Scottish Government actively supports community ownership of energy generation assets through its Community and Renewable Energy Scheme, resulting in spreading the wider economic benefit to communities in which energy generation is taking place.

What should Scotland do better to achieve this Goal?

Affordable and clean energy are the cornerstones of all climate change mitigation approaches. Scotland has a strong political commitment to net-zero carbon by 2045, but a significant increase in supporting policies and action is required and also a re-allocation of funding. Government can do more – tighter targets are needed on energy efficiency and fuel poverty with supporting regulation to drive self-funded households to take energy efficiency measures. Also, the Scottish Government should dedicate greater public funding to helping the fuel poor. At a UK level, energy policies are needed which create a framework for much greater renewable energy generation and which, at the same time, protects the most vulnerable consumers. Local authorities must lead the planning for low carbon heat and local renewable energy generation. Business can do more – more significant strides in improving businesses' energy efficiency and in using low carbon heat should be made which would result in more affordable energy for all. The energy industry needs to ensure that all consumers receive an excellent service. The building industry needs to significantly improve the quality of building work for the installation of energy efficiency measures.

Third sector and communities can do more – affordable and clean energy should be considered as an important element of their wider work. Partnerships need to be forged between support agencies to ensure that vulnerable customers benefit from the specialist support available from Home Energy Scotland. Third sector organisation and local communities are seen by householders as trusted intermediaries and can therefore play a key role in supporting the delivery of energy efficiency programmes. Communities should participate in a more direct delivery of clean energy through community and shared ownership of energy generation assets.⁸ Individuals can do more – everyone in Scotland can make changes in how they use energy at home and at work which will help deliver cleaner

Ensure access to affordable, reliable, sustainable and modern energy for all

energy. By turning down the thermostat, turning off lights, and not leaving electric equipment on standby overall demand is reduced and the proportion of clean energy increased.

Case study — support against fuel poverty

Mrs B had bought her home under right-to-buy from East Lothian Council many years ago. She is an elderly pensioner with mobility issues and other disabilities. She struggled to keep her home warm because of the old heating system. She also worried about going into debt over fuel costs and therefore limited her fuel use. This had a negative impact on her health. With support from an Affordable Warmth Advisor by Changeworks, she was able to access support from Home Energy Scotland through the Scottish Government's National Fuel Poverty scheme delivered by Warmworks. Her home was fitted with new gas-central heating and her loft insulated. The Affordable Warmth Advisor supported her in learning how to use the new system, to set up a gas account, and to change her electricity tariff. Mrs B would have struggled with these tasks on her own.

As a result, the comfort of her home was significantly improved and with the fuels bill expected to be £320 lower per year, Mrs B felt confident in having her heating on. In a follow-up visit six months later, Mrs B reported that her visits to the doctor had decreased and that she was happy to welcome her neighbour into her home, now that it was no longer cold and damp.

Author

Teresa Bray, Chief Executive at Changeworks and former member of the Scottish Government's Strategic Fuel Poverty Working Group

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² ibid

³ Scottish Government. (2011) Scotland's Census. Online from <https://www.scotlandscensus.gov.uk>

⁴ The Energy Saving Trust. (2018) Energy Performance Certificates. Online from <https://www.energysavingtrust.org.uk/home-energy-efficiency/energy-performance-certificates>

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⁶ Scottish Government. (2018) Home Energy Efficiency Programmes for Scotland: delivery report 2016-2017. Online from <https://www.gov.scot/publications/home-energy-efficiency-programmes-scotland-delivery-report-2016-17/>

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Promote sustained, inclusive and sustainable economic growth, full and productive employment and decent work for all

Scottish Trades Union Congress

The STUC is Scotland's trade union centre. Its purpose is to co-ordinate, develop and articulate the views and policies of the trade union movement in Scotland; reflecting the aspirations of trade unionists as workers and citizens. The STUC represents over 540,000 working people and their families throughout Scotland. It speaks for trade union members in and out of work, in the community and in the workplace. Our affiliated organisations have interests in all sectors of the economy, and our representative structures are constructed to take account of the specific views of women members, young members, Black members, LGBT+ members, and members with a disability, as well as retired and unemployed workers.

How is Scotland doing against this Goal?

While the UK and Scottish Government are quick to point to record levels of employment, a look behind headline figures illuminates real issues about the extent of decent work in Scotland. Wages remain below 2008 levels, representing the longest pay squeeze in 200 years. Real wages are not forecast to return to 2008 levels until 2024. While there was some pay growth last year, it is concentrated amongst top earners, particularly in finance. The labour market is increasingly precarious. Underemployment remains above 2008 levels. Self-employment represents more than 10% of the workforce and a significant amount of this is low-paid and/or bogus self-employment. Official statistics show that across the UK zero-hour contracts have increased from 143,000 in 2008 to 844,000 in 2018. In Scotland, last year 41,000 people reported stress, anxiety or depression caused or made worse by work. This is an increase of 33,000 over the previous year. While mental health issues receive increasing levels of welcome attention, there is a lack of focus on the workplace as a driver of mental ill-health.

Women, disabled people and ethnic minorities fare worse on almost all of the indicators above. There are also a number of issues which are not picked up by official statistics. For example, the Better than Zero campaign, housed at the STUC, receives daily stories from young hospitality workers about bullying, harassment and unpaid wages, indicating a structural problem in this sector. In sum, the reality for many in Scotland is low-paid, increasingly precarious, and stressful work. These issues feed into a number of economy-wide problems. Productivity has stalled since 2010; poverty and inequality have increased in the last three years and have done so from already high levels; in-work poverty is an increasing problem; and household debt is on the rise.

Is Scotland committed to achieving this Goal?

In recent years the Scottish Government have revised their economic strategy to show a clearer commitment to tackling inequality and promoting 'inclusive growth'. They established the independent Fair Work Convention, co-chaired by the STUC's General Secretary, Grahame Smith. The Government have subsequently developed a Fair Work Action Plan which commits the Scottish Government to 'Fair Work First' by 2021 so that grants, funding streams and business support will require employers to meet a range of fair work criteria. Crucially, the Scottish Government have recognised the importance of employee voice and collective bargaining in achieving fair work. This is demonstrated by the inclusion of a new collective bargaining indicator within the Government's National Performance Framework. This approach stands in stark contrast to the policies of the UK Government, who have sought to restrict trade union activities through the Trade Union Act in 2016. However, while there is high-level commitment to 'fair work', there are a number of areas where the Scottish Government's commitment has not led to action. For example,

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the Scottish Government provide hundreds of millions of pounds tax cuts to businesses through the Small Business Bonus Scheme (SBBS) and non-domestic rates relief. About £1.3 billion of public funds have been committed to the SBBS in the past ten years. The 2018/19 budget set out a total Non-Domestic Rates package of relief worth a record £720 million. Much of this goes to businesses that do not provide fair or decent work, for example many businesses in the hospitality sector. It is unclear whether the Scottish Government's 'Fair Work First' approach will extend to these tax cuts.

What should Scotland do better to achieve this Goal?

At the heart of fair work considerations is the need for effective voice for workers to raise demands and take action for change. This means increasing trade union membership and widening collective bargaining coverage. The STUC recognises that employment law is reserved. However, whilst this being the case the public sector in Scotland can and should support fair work through its commissioning and procurement processes. The STUC welcomes the 'Fair Work First' commitment, but believes that this should be expanded as quickly as possible to consider adherence to collective bargaining agreements.

The Government should also support improvements in pay and terms and conditions for outsourced workers who deliver public services, for example in the social care sector and the early learning and childcare sector. A recent report by the Fair Work Convention exposed the poor practices across the social care sector, including high levels of insecurity and low rates of pay. While the STUC welcomes the Scottish Government's work to implement the living wage, this approach does not recognise the level of skill or responsibility associated with jobs in social care, nor does it deal with insecure work or other issues associated with job design. The STUC welcomes the recommendation in the Fair Work Convention's report to create a sectoral forum which agrees a minimum set of terms and conditions for social care workers in Scotland. This would help recognise the true value and contribution that this predominantly female workforce makes to the Scottish economy.

Similarly, workers in early learning and childcare who are employed directly by the public sector and therefore are covered by collective bargaining agreements, are paid on average £13,000 more a year than a woman doing exactly the same job in the private sector where no collective agreement applies. Raising pay in the private and third sector to the living wage – the Scottish Government is committed to this as part of its plans to increase funded places in early learning and childcare centres and nurseries to 1140 hours a year, from the current 600 hours a year – would do little to close this gap or properly recognise the value of this workforce. The childcare expansion should seek to correct the issue of low pay by supporting the expansion of collective bargaining coverage through the creation of a sectoral agreement that guarantees minimum terms and conditions for all workers regardless of setting.

Case study – precarious work and decent work

The STUC is currently undertaking research into precarious work and the impact on workers' facing a lack of decent and secure work. The report is due to be published in summer 2019. Below are a couple of quotes from research participants which illustrate the lack of decent work in Scotland. 72,000 people in Scotland are on zero-hour contracts while 122,000 are on temporary contracts. Larger numbers still are underemployed and/or in low-paid self-employment.

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'Because I wasn't guaranteed the hours I would have to do 2 jobs, so the first job I worked in a bar, so I was maybe finishing at like 4 in the morning, we weren't allowed to keep our tips and then I was getting up for my other shift at maybe 9 sometimes, and that was always a struggle.' Young worker

More than half of women and three quarters of LGBT+ people have experienced sexual harassment in the workplace.

'I got offered £15 for a job last night that I will guarantee you they earn far more than £15 for somewhere in Amsterdam... Imagine if you were sitting in an office and a colleague or one of the people that you see leaned over and was like I'll give you £15 if you [...] you'd have them arrested. In hospitality I was just like go away, you're weird.' Female hospitality worker

As detailed earlier, these labour market issues feed into a number of economy-wide problems – low productivity, increasing poverty and inequality, and a failure to ensure living standards increase in-line with economic growth.

Further reading

- STUC report on decent work in social care: 'Scotland's care crisis'
- STUC report on decent work in the low-carbon and renewable energy sector: 'Broken Promises and Offshored Jobs: a report into employment in the low-carbon and renewable energy economy'
- Joint STUC and Scottish Government report on digitalisation and its impact on work: 'Technological Change and the Scottish Labour Market'

Author

Francis Stuart, Policy Officer at the Scottish Trades Union Congress

Promote sustained, inclusive and sustainable economic growth, full and productive employment and decent work for all

Joseph Rowntree Foundation

The Joseph Rowntree Foundation is a social change organisation working to end poverty in the UK. Our work covers four outcomes areas: more people want to solve poverty, understand and take action; more people find a route out of poverty through work; more people find a route out of poverty through a better system of social security; and more people live in decent and affordable homes. The Foundation has a team in Scotland working to solve poverty through these outcomes in a Scottish context.

How is Scotland doing against this Goal?

Currently, one million people in Scotland are in poverty, and many of us will find ourselves or our families within the grasp of poverty, and the harm it causes to health and wellbeing, at some point in our life. Despite reaching record levels of employment, Scotland has also reached record levels of in-work poverty. These two statistics, seen together, prove that Scotland does not have a satisfactory track record in relation to Goal 8, specifically Goal Target 8.5.

In work poverty rate - Scotland

Source: Households Below Average Income (JRF Analysis)

Working age employment rate - Scotland

Source: NOMIS

There are a number of groups that the Scottish Government itself has highlighted as being at particular risk of poverty, specifically in relation to children. These are groups that face barriers to full participation in the labour market and/or discrimination, including lone parents, families where there is a disability, and minority ethnic families. To meet Goal 8, these families need to be prioritised to ensure that they are not excluded from

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economic growth and decent jobs due to factors outwith their control. In measuring progress towards this Goal, it is important that those who face significant barriers to paid work due to ill-health, disability, or caring responsibilities are also given recognition of their role in economy and society. Without significant progress towards this Goal, Scotland risks not just harm to society. As well as limiting our productive capacity as workers, lack of progress on the Goal also places immeasurable strain on public spending due to the knock-on effects of low income – such as poor health, leading to more reliance on services like the NHS. It is very obvious that without sustained efforts to make the economy and labour market work for all, Scotland will undermine its own future potential at great cost. At the moment, it is not clear that all in the Scottish Government are aligned to this Goal – for example, the recent Poverty and Inequality Commission report ‘Delivering Inclusive Growth in Scotland’¹ which found that the national strategy is not being easily understood or translated through to action on the ground – so that we see policy making which tackles the consequences of low income, rather than its causes.

Is Scotland committed to achieving this Goal?

We welcome that the Scottish Government has put the principles of Goal 8 into its Economic Strategy,² badged as ‘Inclusive Growth’. As part of this, an outcomes framework has been proposed around five themes: productivity; population; participation; people; and place. The sentiments expressed by the Scottish Government in the notion of ‘Inclusive Growth’ are encouraging, but the signs that this is leading to different patterns of decision making in all areas of government, and hence accelerating progress towards the Inclusive Growth outcomes, are less clear. However, within particular areas of government there has been clear vision and action. Labour market access and fair work are areas that the Scottish Government still has only limited powers over, but examples such as Fair Start Scotland, championing of Living Wage accreditation, Fair Work First criteria for awarding contracts, and innovative programmes such as the Returners scheme for women who wish to return to the labour market, show there is policy commitment to match political will, even if these initiatives are fairly small in scale.

What should Scotland do better to achieve this Goal?

Ideally, government policy should ensure that all spending and policy decisions are cognisant of the inclusive growth outcomes. Actions that do not play a role in meeting these outcomes or even perversely work against them should only be taken forward as economic policy if there is an explicit rationale given as to why. This applies to both national and local governments in Scotland. As an example, North Ayrshire Council have embraced this approach to decision making. Together with the Scottish Government, the Council helped to pilot an Inclusive Growth Diagnostic³ to understand what constrains inclusive growth and where additional activity is needed. They have used this information to guide Council spending decisions at a strategic level. However, despite Scottish Government support for the diagnostic tool and for other local and regional examples, we have not yet seen evidence of an equivalent exercise taking place at national level. The way that the Scottish Government directly invests at local level also appears to lack a particular regard to tackling poverty. For example, it is difficult to find explicit commitments at scale to boost employment and progression for people in poverty in City Region/Growth Deals.

Additionally, there needs to be greater policy coherence to guide preventative spend to ensure that we are not storing up problems that then need to be dealt with later on, potentially at greater cost. For example, health spending in Scotland is now around 50% of the entire devolved budget. It is well understood that low incomes are contributory

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factors to poorer health, and once people are ill they find it much harder to find and remain in employment. Similarly, the focus on reducing the poverty-related attainment gap by spending more on schools perhaps overlooks the importance of a stable home environment and how it can be put at risk by insecure housing and poor jobs.

To achieve Goal 8, employers in all sectors must look after their workforce in order to maximise productivity and reduce turnover of staff. For those in lower paid work, this often does not appear to be the case. In some cases, this does require the reconsideration of business models to focus more on long-term growth and resilience rather than short-term returns. The enterprise agencies in Scotland have a clear role to play in fostering this approach.

Case study — in-work poverty

In-work poverty has far-reaching impacts on people in Scotland. Most working-age families in poverty have a family member working, yet within that there are a huge range of different experiences. These range from lone parents who work part-time to balance care responsibilities, underemployment amongst men and women who cannot find enough hours to make ends meet, to households where there are other barriers to adults working full-time and/or being able to sustain attachment to the labour market. Often the policy response focusses on pay. In Scotland one approach has been the promotion of the voluntary living wage. Other issues that are recognised by the Scottish Government but have seen less action, are work intensity (hours worked per adult in household) and tax/benefits for working people. In-work poverty is symptomatic of a labour market that does not generate 'decent work' for all. It leaves many people fighting against strong currents ranging from cost and availability of transportation, affordability and flexibility of pre-school and after-school care, to requirements for care for members of their family. Coupled with this, the hours that employers are prepared to offer and flexibility requirements that employers expect mean that it is a constant struggle to keep everything together and to make ends meet. We are seeing that more and more people are doing all they can to be economically active and all that the social security system expects of them in terms of conditionality, but are still finding that they are not moving out of poverty's grasp. There is a real risk that people in this position become trapped, particularly in industries where progression opportunities are few and far between. The Resolution Foundation has produced research showing that Scotland had marginally better outcomes over a decade than the UK as a whole, but still the odds of fully escaping low pay are just 1:5.⁴ The longer people are in poverty the greater the harm caused, particularly for children. It simply cannot be right that our economic system leaves families with no option but to be in poverty.

Further reading

- Scotland's Inclusive Growth Outcomes Framework: <http://www.inclusivegrowth.scot/resources/data-and-analysis/2018/06/inclusive-growth-outcomes-framework/>

Author

Emma Congreve, Senior Economist (Scotland) at the Joseph Rowntree Foundation

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³North Ayrshire Council. (2018) Cabinet meeting notes. Point 3. Online from <https://north-ayrshire.cmis.uk.com/north-ayrshire/Document.ashx?czJKcaeAi5tUFLIDL2UE4zNRBcoShgo=eGtnkJNdRSnvmYJWfC5fOmqqbbolbXq3Mw6TW%2bQ9pFc9CpY9DzT6FHg%3d%3d&rUzwRPF%2bZ3zd4E7lkn8LW%3d%3d=pwRE6AGJFLDNih225F5QMqWQCzPHwdhUfCZ%2fLUQzgA2uL5jNRG4jdQ%3d%3d&mCTIbCubSFFxSDGW9lXnlG%3d%3d=hFflUdN3100%3d&kCx1AnS9%2fpWZQ4ODXFvdEw%3d%3d=hFflUdN3100%3d&uJovDxwdjMPoYv%2bAJvYtyA%3d%3d=ctNJFF55vVA%3d&FgPIIEJYlotS%2bYGoBi5oIA%3d%3d=NhDURQburHA%3d&d9QjjOag1Pd993jsyOJqFvmyB7XOCSQK=ctNJFF55vVA%3d&WgewmoAfeNR9xqBux0rIQ8Za60lavYmz=ctNJFF55vVA%3d&WgewmoAfeNQ16B2MHuCPMRKZMwaG1PaO=ctNJFF55vVA%3d>

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Build resilient infrastructure, promote inclusive and sustainable industrialization and foster innovation

Social Enterprise Scotland

Social enterprises, as leaders in business innovation, exist to build an inclusive and sustainable economy. Social Enterprise Scotland is the voice of social enterprise – uniting social enterprises and their supporters in a strong campaigning force – and is the gateway to Scotland’s social enterprise community. SES is an independent and membership-led organisation, built and controlled by social enterprises.

How is Scotland doing against this Goal?

Scotland is leading the way globally in many areas of social enterprise support and development, as well as in other business and economic innovations. The Social Enterprise Census 2017 demonstrated a thriving social enterprise community in Scotland with 5,600 social enterprises, employing the equivalent of 81,357 full-time workers. The total annual income of social enterprises was £3.8bn and the net worth of Scotland’s social enterprises stood at £5bn. The economic contribution, in terms of gross value added, of Scotland’s social enterprises amounted to £2bn.¹ Most social enterprises are small in scale, with less than £100,000 in turnover, according to the Census. They face the same challenges as private sector small businesses, but have the added role of achieving a social or environmental purpose. They also understand the challenge of attracting funding and affordable investment. Positively, Scotland and the UK have a range of social investment providers such as Big Issue Invest, Social Investment Scotland, Charity Bank, and Triodos Bank. Credit unions may play a greater role in affordable investment in the future. There are significant, but manageable challenges to the further development of social enterprises in Scotland. They include the need to further open up opportunities for public sector procurement and for the delivery of public services to social enterprises, and getting into private sector supply chains and other private sector partnerships.

The specialist Partnership for Procurement service is helping social enterprises access public sector supply chains and contribute towards infrastructure development. In addition, increasing numbers of big private sector companies are working with social enterprises to provide catering and other services, but much more needs to be done.

There is also an ongoing challenge to increase public and media understanding of social enterprise business models. However, over the past few years, many social enterprises have become well-known – examples are The Big Issue, Social Bite, The Wise Group, Divine Chocolate, Kibble, Glasgow Housing Association, the Eden Project, Capital Credit Union, Hey Girls, and the Homeless World Cup – and with them public awareness of this business model has grown. Recently, we have witnessed the emergence or resurgence of other business models such as B Corporations and co-operatives. Also, some big businesses are now trying to go beyond basic corporate social responsibility. These newer business models are a challenge to social enterprises, but objectives are essentially shared between them and different business models should work together to achieve, for example, Goal 9.

The development of innovative business models is being pro-actively supported by the Scottish Government through funding and investment and free, practical business support. Initiatives like the specialist Just Enterprise for social enterprises, Scotland Can B for new, mission-led businesses, the Scottish Business Pledge, and the Real Living Wage are driving this agenda. To achieve Goal 9, it is important that we ensure that all types of businesses, large and small, are on board with doing business differently and building an inclusive economy. This is perhaps the biggest challenge.

Build resilient infrastructure, promote inclusive and sustainable industrialization and foster innovation

Is Scotland committed to achieving this Goal?

Policy support for social enterprise, employee ownership, B Corporations, the real Living Wage, and fair work, and other economic innovations like the Scottish National Investment Bank (SNIB) is strong. This is from both the Scottish Government and Parliament, as well as from all political parties in Parliament. In terms of infrastructure there has been a decisive move in procurement towards sustainability and consideration of social and environmental impact. Support for this agenda is strong from the Scottish Government. There are a number of, for example, construction companies that are helping drive forward sustainability and social enterprise in supply chains. Local authorities and other public bodies have a role to play as well. Many local authorities have officers dedicated to social enterprise support. Some, but not all, local authority Business Gateway services have specialist social enterprise advisors.

In addition, there have been Public-Social Partnerships with the NHS. In terms of the private sector there is much potential. Social Enterprise Scotland have recently worked on a booklet highlighting some existing good practice case studies in this regard. This is all having a positive impact on the growth and development of social enterprises and the inclusive economy agenda as stipulated in Target 2 of Goal 9.

There must be a sustained focus on the responsibilities of local authorities, other public bodies, and the private sector. Further action should be taken to get them on board with building better businesses and an inclusive economy.

What should Scotland do better to achieve this Goal?

Innovators need to stop thinking and working separately so that we can begin to link up the pieces of the jigsaw that make up innovation, sustainability and the development of a mainstream social economy. For example, there are direct links between various economic and business innovations for building an inclusive economy. In other words, business models such as social enterprises, co-operatives, charities, credit unions, B Corporations, mutuals, and ethical and green businesses are linked to the real living wage, universal basic income, tax justice, flexible working, local currencies, and pay ratios within organisations. All of these innovations aim to achieve an inclusive, sustainable economy and a fairer, more equal society. If they exist alone then fundamental change in the economy will not happen. We need to promote and implement these types of policies in local communities across Scotland. We can learn from campaign groups such as Social Enterprise Scotland and Social Enterprise UK, Tax Justice UK, trade unions, Cooperatives UK, PB Scotland (participatory budgeting), the Bristol Pound and the credit union movement. We can also learn from other countries. For example, Germany has a national investment bank; the USA has large credit unions; Spain has, with Mondragon, large-scale co-operatives in the Basque Country; and various countries across the world have introduced or experimented with universal basic income schemes.

Such change requires leadership. This should primarily come from civic society and social economy organisations. They should demonstrate to government and the public and private sectors a better way forward. Government must play the role of facilitator, providing both a welcoming and empowering policy environment and the financial resources to achieve this change.

Despite the progress outlined above we still have not placed Scotland on a fundamentally different path in terms of business and the economy. We need a strong economy based on localism, environmental sustainability, high pay for all, and strong social security. This

Build resilient infrastructure, promote inclusive and sustainable industrialization and foster innovation

can only happen by ensuring that social enterprise and other ethical, green and mission-led business models become the normal way of doing business. This has not yet been achieved. If we do not achieve this fundamental change in our economic system and business models and culture then the outcome will be increasing inequality, democratic decline and further environmental harm.

Case study – community-owned enterprises

Community-owned enterprises are a great example of business innovation and of building an inclusive economy. This includes food co-operatives, development trusts, community-owned energy companies, and social housing organisations – all being run by and for the community. There are many examples – the Kinning Park Complex in Glasgow; the Sleat Community Trust in Skye; Eilean Eisdeal on Easdale Island; and the Inverclyde Development Trust. While they may sometimes have a small financial turnover, their social and economic impact, particularly in a small community, can be huge. When land, buildings and businesses are community-owned, they regularly lead to additional innovations and a renaissance in economic activity. One community ownership project often has a ripple effect and leads to other activities. Scotland has a particular issue with land ownership being concentrated in a few private sector hands. This has been proven to hold up economic activity, regeneration, housing and a range of other economic and environmental activities. Community-owned businesses operate in the interests of the local community and can unleash this potential. 'Local' government in Scotland is not local. With only 32 Councils this compares badly with other similar sized European countries. Therefore, with this lack of genuine local government these types of businesses are helping to revive local democracy too.

Further reading

- Cooperatives UK: <https://www.uk.coop/>
- Scottish Business Pledge: <https://scottishbusinesspledge.scot/>
- Scotland Can B: <https://canb.scot/>
- Social Enterprise UK: <https://www.socialenterprise.org.uk/>
- Development Trusts Association Scotland: <https://dtascot.org.uk/>
- Community Ownership Support Service: <https://dtascommunityownership.org.uk/>
- Tax Justice UK: <http://www.taxjustice.uk/>
- Bristol Pound: <https://bristolpound.org/>
- Association of British Credit Unions: <https://www.abcul.coop/home>

Author

Duncan Thorp, Policy and Communications Manager at Social Enterprise Scotland

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Reduce inequality within and among countries

Fife Centre for Equalities

Fife Centre for Equalities (FCE), funded by Fife Council, started in 2014 with the vision to inspire and enable everyone we work with to take action that makes Fife a more equal, fairer place to live, work and study. FCE's mission is to develop a harmonised approach to build a collective voice to champion equality, diversity, inclusion and social justice. Our values are to work with honesty, integrity, respect and transparency, and we strive to demonstrate a fully inclusive approach in everything we do. We want everyone we work with to share these values in the belief that they will help make Fife a fairer and more equal place.

How is Scotland doing against this Goal?

While income inequality impacts on all age groups in society, its long-term effects are worse on children as it impacts their development and future prospects. In 2017, the risk of poverty in the UK for people under 18 was at 21.3%,¹ the highest since 2008.

The situation in Scotland appears not to be worsening at present and is relatively better than across Great Britain,² but there is still a high incidence of child poverty, and a high poverty gap. Between 2015 and 2018, it is estimated that 24% of children in Scotland (240,000 children each year) were living in relative poverty after housing costs.³

In 2016/2017, the 10% most deprived areas in Scotland had levels of child poverty at 34.9%, compared to 3.7% in the 10% least deprived,⁴ a gap of 30.5%. In our local authority area, the gap in Fife was of 30.7% for the same period. However, our position is that 'reducing inequality' should involve understanding and addressing the magnitude of the gaps between populations as well as 'proportions of population' in poverty. Not including equality and protected characteristics in 'reducing inequality'/'anti-poverty' measures is, in our perspective, counter-productive as this further contributes to siloed policy making or communities of practice. For instance, relative poverty rates after housing costs are double (38%) for Mixed, Black or Black British and Other ethnicities compared to the whole population (19%), and over twice higher (41%) for Muslim adults compared to adults overall (18%).⁵ Universal Credit has had a disproportionate impact on disabled people.⁶ Economic inequality and barriers to equality of opportunity are closely related agendas. Social mobility is limited in Scotland, as a person's job and life chances are still determined by their socio-economic status at birth. In 2018, 55% of people in professional/managerial occupations had parents with similar occupations, compared to 32.4% with parents from working class backgrounds. On a positive note, this gap has narrowed 28% to 23% over the past four years, while it has remained stagnant at 26% across Britain.

Is Scotland committed to achieving this Goal?

There is not enough commitment behind this Goal, as the laws to ensure equal opportunity and tackle inequality through anti-discriminatory laws, policies and practices are difficult to enforce by individuals who have few resources to afford legal fees and have had reduced access to legal aid in recent years. In force since 2018, the Fairer Scotland Duty asks for 'active consideration' and 'due regard' to socio-economic considerations of the Equality Act 2010. However, there is no legal requirement to involve communities in meeting the Fairer Scotland Duty, and this allows for great variation in practice across policy areas and local authorities. Gender pay gap reporting is worth considering in this instance. The reporting is mandatory for companies in Great Britain (not Northern Ireland) with more than 250 employees. There are issues with how accurate this reporting is and also with how well it is enforced across different employers, setting precedents for some sectors (e.g. tech, agriculture, some large private employers) to be less committed to SDG 10 and also SDG 5 (Gender Equality). Nevertheless, it creates a baseline that can be acted upon to tackle

Reduce inequality within and among countries

inequality as it is mandatory and not dependent on 'active considerations'. Disability and race pay gaps do not currently have the same level of political or policy commitment.

What should Scotland do better to achieve this Goal?

We could do better by adopting a unified approach to pay gap reporting across protected characteristics and thus minimise the time or cost of assessing and implementing various evidence gaps⁷ and diminish disparity between groups attempting to validate their experience, or tackle inequality in isolation and competition. We would like to see employers becoming more transparent and actively become more diverse (e.g. by adopting the '50:50 by 2020' voluntary scheme) when it comes to the workings and memberships of their pay and remuneration committees.⁸ There should be more regulation and mandatory training and guidance for equality and diversity policies for both SMEs and large employers, including support for adopting positive employment policies (e.g. Disability Confident or the Living Wage). This is in order to tackle the longstanding barriers to employment for people with protected characteristics at the recruitment stage. To do better in this Goal, we would need to give tangible support to employers who are adopting inclusive recruitment practices.

Case study – the impact of benefit changes

When we responded to the UK Public Accounts Committee in July 2018,⁹ we raised concerns about increasing economic inequality of disabled people who transitioned from the full Employment and Support Allowance legacy system to Universal Credit. For the same set of conditions,¹⁰ disabled people were worse off by £67 per week, an amount which is directly comparable to the cost of weekly food spend per household.

Author detail

Elric Honoré, Development Officer at Fife Centre for Equalities

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⁷ Scottish Government. (2017) Scotland's equality evidence strategy 2017-2021. Online from <https://www.gov.scot/publications/scotlands-equality-evidence-strategy-2017-2021/pages/10/>

⁸ Office of the First Ministers. (2015) 50/50 by 2020 – Diversity in the Boardroom. Online from <https://firstminister.gov.scot/5050-by-2020-working-for-diversity-in-the-boardroom/>

⁹ Fife Centre for Equalities. (2018) Written Response to the Universal Credit Inquiry. Online from <https://centreforequalities.org.uk/wp-content/uploads/2018/07/FCE-Written-Response-to-the-Universal-Credit-PAC-Inquiry-JUL18-.pdf>

¹⁰ Both claimants receive PIP Daily Living components at the standard rate, live alone and no one is claiming Carers Allowance in respect of them. The only difference is Person A is on ESA, Person B is on UC.

Reduce inequality within and among countries

Oxfam

Oxfam is an international confederation of 19 organizations networked together in more than 90 countries, as part of a global movement for change, to build a future free from the injustice of poverty. Under the banner 'Even It Up', Oxfam drives the inequality debate at global, regional and national levels. In Scotland, Oxfam has campaigned for, and worked closely with, the Poverty and Inequality Commission. We have also made the case for a more 'human economy'¹ and have supported the development of the 'Wellbeing Economy Governments', an international platform seeking to embed well-being outcomes in economic policy.²

How is Scotland doing against this Goal?

Extreme and growing economic inequality is a global issue, and Scotland is far from immune. Recent figures reveal the incomes of the top 10% of the population are over a quarter higher than the bottom 40% put together, and trends show that income inequality in Scotland is deepening.³ Whilst there is welcome political momentum around tackling poverty,⁴ much of this agenda focusses only on lifting those at the lower end of the income distribution over the poverty line while doing little to address the income and wealth inequality across the whole distribution.⁵ Oxfam research has shown that in the UK, since the 1960s, poverty rates tend to be higher when income inequality is higher, showing us that we cannot tackle Scotland's poverty problem in isolation.⁶

Evidence suggests the level of inequality in Scotland is not so different from other parts of the UK. While Scotland has a lower Gini Coefficient⁷ (0.31) than Great Britain (0.39), the trends over the last two decades have followed a similar pattern. Latest figures suggest inequality in Scotland is now higher than it was at the time of the Scotland Act in 1998, and closer to the score for Great Britain as a whole.⁸ Whilst there are high levels of income inequality, wealth – including financial, property, pensions and physical assets – is even more unequally distributed. The wealth held by the top 10% of households is around five times greater than the wealth of the bottom half combined.⁹ On the one hand, median household wealth has increased by 28%;¹⁰ on the other hand, a fifth of Scots do not have any personal savings, putting them at greater risk of financial shocks.¹¹

But inequality is about much more than economic inequality. In Scotland, there are spatial inequalities; inequalities across the life course; intergenerational inequalities; and inequality between different groups. Commentary on all of the above is beyond the scope of this report, but analysis of Scotland's poverty statistics shows that women, lone parents, those who are disabled, and those from black and minority ethnic groups, are disproportionately represented at the bottom end of the distribution.¹² Goal Indicator 10.2 focusses on the promotion of social, economic and political inclusion of all. Equality and Human Rights Commission's quintennial 'Is Scotland Fairer?' report includes a summary of Scotland's progress on political participation. In 2018 the Commission found that women, people from ethnic minority groups, and disabled people continue to be under-represented in all areas of public life, including the Scottish Parliament.¹³ Until we address inequalities of power and political participation, progress on addressing economic inequality will be hindered.

Is Scotland committed to achieving this Goal?

There is little doubt that policy-making on inequality is more progressive in Scotland than at the UK level. Indicators for this are, for example:

- A more progressive income tax schedule with five bands;¹⁴
- The inclusion of tackling inequality within Scotland's Economic Strategy;¹⁵
- The Fairer Scotland Duty;¹⁶

Reduce inequality within and among countries

- The Community Empowerment (Scotland) Act 2015;¹⁷
- The Fairer Scotland Action Plan;¹⁸ The Child Poverty (Scotland) Act (2017)¹⁹ and the Tackling Child Poverty Delivery Plan (2018);²⁰
- The Scottish Government's role in establishing the 'Wellbeing Economy Governments' and supporting the 'beyond growth' movement in Scotland and internationally.²¹

The appointment of an Independent Poverty and Inequality Advisor and the establishment of the Poverty and Inequality Commission have been important steps to ensure that reducing inequality remains on the political agenda. However, despite inequality remaining central to political discourse, not enough concrete action is being taken and wealth inequality specifically does not feature as much as it perhaps should. There is a problem regarding data availability to evaluate policy actions. In its assessment of progress since the Independent Poverty and Inequality Advisor's 2016 'Shifting the Curve' report, the Commission found that 'there is a lack of hard data, with little in the way of setting baselines or measuring progress'.²²

The National Performance Framework should help set those baselines and measure progress and the reduction of inequality has been embedded in the Framework since 2007, expressed as the 'Solidarity Target'. But the extent to which the NPF maps onto the Global Goals – and Goal 10 in particular – is questionable.²³ For example, the NPF contains no indicators to measure progress on discrimination and harassment, labour share of GDP, or financial soundness indicators.^{24,25} Furthermore, the NPF is a framework for measuring progress and cannot on its own deliver progress. Since the Solidarity Target was introduced, we have seen inequality widen, not reduce. More work must be done to translate the outcomes into meaningful policy action, with resources committed in a transparent way.

What should Scotland do better to achieve this Goal?

Although many important policy levers remain reserved to Westminster, key devolved powers that can make a difference to inequality include income tax and social security powers; education and skills; economic development; public procurement; planning; housing and childcare.²⁶ Scotland must take decisive action on the following:

1. Scotland must move beyond ambition and deliver action

The task of reducing inequality must be shared across all Scottish Government portfolios with specific actions identified within each to deliver meaningful progress on the Palma Ratio specifically. The NPF provides Scotland with national outcomes and indicators, now we need to see clear actions that will shrink the gap between rich and poor.

2. Scotland must make bolder spending decisions that tackle poverty and inequality

Recent analysis has shown that less than one percent of the budget is directly targeted at low income households.²⁷ If we are serious about reducing inequality, Scotland needs to make some ambitious spending decisions that put money in the pockets of those at the lower end of the income distribution. One opportunity to do this is the planned Income Supplement for low income families, a very welcome commitment in the Child Poverty Delivery Plan.

3. Scotland must take redistributing wealth seriously

Tax powers exist in Scotland beyond income tax and these should be explored as a tool for redistributing wealth more evenly. Since the Commission on Local Tax Reform²⁸ there has been little progress in line with the recommendations of that group.

Reduce inequality within and among countries

4. Scotland needs more action from business and employers

There has been growing interest in the establishment of pay policy.²⁹ The Scottish Parliament does not have the power to legislate in this area but it could utilise its influence and 'moral-suasion' to encourage firms to adopt good practice and greater transparency.

Case study — in-work poverty

Inequality in Scotland should be seen in the context of widening global inequality. Oxfam's annual report – released to coincide with the World Economic Forum in Davos – reveals staggering levels of global economic inequality. The wealth of the world's billionaires increased by \$900 billion in the last year; as much as \$2.5 billion a day.³⁰ The report highlighted the experiences of garment workers in Vietnam, who make shoes for consumers in more affluent countries, but are not paid enough to support the cost of living:

'I'd like my son to have shoes like these, but he can't. I think he'd want them, and I feel sorry for him. The shoes are very pretty. You know that one pair of shoes that we make is valued more than our whole month's salary.' – Lan, garment worker, Vietnam

In-work poverty is an issue that is experienced in Scotland too, and is on the rise, reaching an all-time high in 2015-18 with 60% of those in poverty living in working households.³¹ The following case study from A Menu for Change³² – a three-year project exploring solutions to food insecurity – shows the realities of in work poverty:

'...my partner's always in and out of work, that's always just temporary contracts, getting paid off, and it's never like permanent, you don't know if he's gonna' go in today and come back without a job [...]. We would always be asking family for money or they'd help us out with shopping, but it just got to the point where we didn't feel like we could ask anybody anymore, 'cause we'd done it so much. But it's not just food, it's running out of gas and electric and stuff, sitting in the dark for a few days and not eating just to make it to payday.' – Harriet, Fife

Further reading

- Public Good or Private Wealth? Universal health, education and other public services reduce the gap between rich and poor, and between women and men. Fairer taxation of the wealthiest can help pay for them (2019) by Man-Kwun Chan, Anam Parvez Butt, Anna Marriott, Elen Ehmke, Didier Jacobs, Julie Seghers, Jaime Atienza, Rebecca Gowland, Max Lawson, Francesca Rhodes: <https://policy-practice.oxfam.org.uk/publications/public-good-or-private-wealth-universal-health-education-and-other-public-servi-620599>
- Reward Work, Not Wealth: To end the inequality crisis, we must build an economy for ordinary working people, not the rich and powerful (2018) by Diego Alejo Vazquez Pimentel, Inigo Macias Aymar and Max Lawson: <https://policy-practice.oxfam.org.uk/publications/reward-work-not-wealth-to-end-the-inequality-crisis-we-must-build-an-economy-fo-620396>
- Everyone's Business: The role of the Scottish Business Pledge in delivering the Global Goals (2018) by Rhiannon Sims: <https://oxfamapps.org/scotland/2018/08/24/2018-08-everyones-business-the-role-of-the-scottish-business-pledge-in-delivering-the-global-goals/>
- Building a More Equal Scotland: Designing Scotland's Poverty and Inequality Commission (2017) by Ryan McQuigg, Francis Stuart, and David Eiser: <https://policy-practice.oxfam.org.uk/publications/search?q=building%20a%20more%20equal%20>

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scotland;sort=publication_date Double Trouble: A review of the relationship between UK poverty and economic inequality (2017) by Abigail McKnight, Magali Duque, Mark Rucci: <https://policy-practice.oxfam.org.uk/publications/double-trouble-a-review-of-the-relationship-between-uk-poverty-and-economic-ine-620373>

- Oxfam Humankind Index: The new measure of Scotland's Prosperity, second results (2013) by Oxfam Scotland: <https://policy-practice.oxfam.org.uk/publications/oxfam-humankind-index-the-new-measure-of-scotlands-prosperity-second-results-293743>
- Our Economy: Towards a new prosperity (2013) Katherine Trebeck and Francis Stuart: <https://policy-practice.oxfam.org.uk/publications/oxfam-humankind-index-the-new-measure-of-scotlands-prosperity-second-results-293743>

Author

Rhiannon Sims, Research and Policy Officer at Oxfam Scotland

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² Wellbeing Economy Governments. (2019) About. Online from <http://wellbeingeconomygovernments.org/>

³ Scottish Government. (2019) Poverty and income inequality in Scotland: 2015-2018. Online from <https://www.gov.scot/publications/poverty-income-inequality-scotland-2015-18/>

⁴ Scottish Government. (2016) Fairer Scotland Action Plan. Online from <https://www.gov.scot/publications/fairer-scotland-action-plan/>

⁵ Scottish Parliament. (2017) Child Poverty (Scotland) Act 2017. Online from <http://www.legislation.gov.uk/asp/2017/6/contents/enacted>

⁶ Oxfam GB. (2017) Double Trouble: A review of the relationship between UK poverty and economic inequality. Online from <https://policy-practice.oxfam.org.uk/publications/double-trouble-a-review-of-the-relationship-between-uk-poverty-and-economic-ine-620373>

⁷ The Gini Coefficient is a commonly used measure of inequality, expressed as a number from zero to one. The nearer the Gini to 1, the higher the level of inequality.

⁸ Pryce and Le Zhang. (2018) Inequality in Scotland: despite Nordic aspirations, things are not improving. Online from <https://theconversation.com/inequality-in-scotland-despite-nordic-aspirations-things-are-not-improving-105307>

⁹ ONS. (2018) Wealth in Great Britain Wave 5: 2014 to 2016. Online from <https://www.ons.gov.uk/releases/wealthgreatbritainwave52014to2016>

¹⁰ The median household total wealth for England rose by 18% to £268,100 between July 2012 to June 2014 and July 2014 to June 2016. In comparison, the median household total wealth for Scotland increased by 28% to £237,600. ONS. (2018) Wealth in Great Britain Wave 5: 2014 to 2016. Online from <https://www.ons.gov.uk/releases/wealthgreatbritainwave52014to2016>

¹¹ BBC. (19 July 2017) Bank survey finds 21% of Scots 'have no savings.' Online from <https://www.bbc.co.uk/news/uk-scotland-scotland-business-40654656>

¹² JRF. (2018) Poverty in Scotland. Online from <https://www.jrf.org.uk/report/poverty-scotland-2018>

¹³ EHRC. (2018) Is Scotland Fairer? The state of equality and human rights 2018. Online from <https://www.equalityhumanrights.com/en/publication-download/scotland-fairer-2018>

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¹⁸ Scottish Government. (2016) Fairer Scotland Action Plan. Online from <https://www.gov.scot/publications/fairer-scotland-action-plan/>

¹⁹ Scottish Parliament. (2016) Child Poverty (Scotland) Act 2017. Online from <http://www.legislation.gov.uk/asp/2017/6/contents/enacted>

²⁰ Scottish Government. (2018) Every child, every chance: tackling child poverty delivery plan 2018-2022. Online from <https://www.gov.scot/publications/child-chance-tackling-child-poverty-delivery-plan-2018-22/>

²¹ Eisenstadt, N. (2016) 'Shifting the curve – a report for the First Minister'. Online from <http://www.gov.scot/Publications/2016/01/1984>

²² Poverty and Inequality Commission. (2019) Scrutiny of progress towards meeting the recommendations of the Independent Poverty and Inequality Advisor. Online from <https://povertyinequality.scot/wp-content/uploads/2019/01/Shifting-the-curve-monitoring-progress-report.pdf>

²³ See, for example: Scottish Environment Link submission to inquiry on the new National Outcomes. Online from https://www.parliament.scot/S5_Environment/Inquiries/05_Scottish_Environment_LINK.pdf

²⁴ SHRC. (2018) Submission: Human Rights and National Performance Framework. Online from <http://www.scottishhumanrights.com/policy-publications/>

²⁵ The recent Newcastle University progress report concluded that the indicators attached to Goal 10 are some of the least well represented in the NPF. Newcastle University (2019) The SDGs and Scotland: a discussion paper and initial analysis

²⁶ Oxfam Scotland. (2017) Building a more equal Scotland: Designing Scotland's Poverty and Inequality Commission. Online from <https://policy-practice.oxfam.org.uk/publications/building-a-more-equal-scotland-designing-scotlands-poverty-and-inequality-commission-620264>

²⁷ Poverty and Inequality Commission. (2019) Poverty and Inequality Commission's response to the Scottish Budget. Online from <https://povertyinequality.scot/publication/poverty-and-inequality-commissions-response-to-the-scottish-budget/>

²⁸ Commission on Local Tax Reform. (2015) Just change. A new approach to local taxation. Online from <http://localtaxcommission.scot/download-our-final-report/>

²⁹ See for example recommendation 2 from the Poverty and Inequality Advisor's first report. Eisenstadt, N. (2016) 'Shifting the curve – a report for the First Minister'. Online from <http://www.gov.scot/Publications/2016/01/1984>

³⁰ Oxfam. (2019) Public Good or Private Wealth? Online from <https://policy-practice.oxfam.org.uk/publications/public-good-or-private-wealth-universal-health-education-and-other-public-services-620599>

³¹ Scottish Government (2019) Scotland poverty and inequality statistics. Online from <https://www.gov.scot/publications/poverty-income-inequality-scotland-2015-18/>

³² Menu for Change. (2019) About. Online from menuforchange.org.uk

Make cities and human settlements inclusive, safe, resilient and sustainable

Built Environment Forum Scotland

Built Environment Forum Scotland (BEFS) is an umbrella body for organisations working in the built environment in Scotland. Drawing on extensive expertise in a membership-led forum, BEFS informs, debates and advocates on the strategic issues, opportunities and challenges facing Scotland's historic and contemporary built environment.

How is Scotland doing against this Goal?

There are an estimated 37,000 empty homes in Scotland, excluding second homes.¹ Ensuring a supply of affordable housing will also necessitate bringing far more empty homes back into use – this is currently taking place only in limited ways due to resource implications. While we welcome all efforts in this area, we think that more can be done. As a 'side effect' of bringing empty homes back into use, urban sprawl, as discussed in Goal Target 11.3, could be decreased and a better-integrated urban environment where people are closer to work, home, transport infrastructure (Goal Target 11.2), and the necessary facilities be created. The recent changes and suggestions for some of Scotland's urban areas in relation to the introduction of Low Emission Zones are a positive step – but further and radical changes are necessary to improve public transport infrastructure to make it a reliable, positive choice for more of Scotland's citizens. Goal Target 11.4 is the only SDG that attempts to address the importance of the world's cultural and natural heritage. With an increasing recognition and understanding of the climate threat – and that imminent action is needed – our current natural and cultural heritage can help to play an ever-increasing role in promoting and increasing sustainability. The recent declaration, by the Climate Change Secretary for the Scottish Government, that there is a climate emergency² is some indication of how seriously this is taken, but more policy action and resource for key agencies to take appropriate action is still needed.

Is Scotland committed to achieving this Goal?

The Scottish Government have a strong community empowerment agenda which has brought in a variety of new rights and responsibilities. In relation to SDG 11, one of the most central elements of this agenda is the Community Right to Buy.³ Funds have been made available to enable communities to buy land and certain assets, but it could be questioned whether the resources and skills necessary to run, maintain, and sustain some of these endeavours have been as equally supported. Only time will tell if this has been an effective use of resources for the long-term. What is clear is that communities need to be genuinely empowered, not burdened by default. Current amendments within the proposals for the Planning (Scotland) Bill⁴ go some way to enforcing the need for greenspace within areas of development, as stipulated in Goal Target 11.7. There are also positive proposals for the formation of Local Place Plans which would enable communities and local people to shape the development of their places – but resourcing and skilling for these proposals still needs to be fully articulated. Historic Environment Scotland's (HES) policies and managing change documents provide guidance and advice for how the historic built environment can be protected and adapted (Goal Target 11.4).⁵ They provide advice for progress with all kinds of building adaptations – but the line between protection and change can often appear as a barrier, rather than as an enabler. Perhaps further positive messaging and case studies from HES will help to remove aspects of concern in relation to adaptation (from improved environmental efficiency to adaptive-reuse).

What should Scotland do better to achieve this Goal?

How older buildings are viewed as part of a sustainable resource to support the SDGs – specifically, how they are assessed for the Energy Performance Certificate (EPC)

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ratings – needs to be reviewed to enable accurate assessment by appropriately skilled assessors for traditional buildings types. Often older buildings, when correctly assessed, provide good standards (that can at times be improved upon) rather than being assessed as merely old and inefficient. The changes that many older buildings could undergo to form more sustainable assets, within more sustainable environments, is undoubtedly hampered by the current VAT rate on refurbishment and repair. The current 0% on new build and 20% on refurbishment and repair does not help the re-use and adaptation of buildings which could become well-placed homes, workplaces, and service providers in often already well-connected places. Retrofit Scotland and Architecture & Design Scotland have acknowledged this as a barrier. It is the role of governments to lead transformative and often difficult change (examples from other areas are seatbelt legislation, smoking regulation, or regulation of cigarette sales) for the greater good. It is the role of the third sector to push governments to raise and implement the standards which meet the needs of the future, not just the now.

Case study – managing and maintaining historic sites and places

The case studies found under the link below are examples of holistic and sustainable approaches to maintaining and managing Scotland’s historic sites and places.

- BEFS. (2019) PROTECT – Care and Protect. <https://www.befs.org.uk/resources/historic-environment-case-studies/care-protect/>

Author

Ailsa Macfarlane, Policy and Advocacy Officer at Built Environment Forum Scotland

¹ Empty Homes Network. (2019) About. Online from https://scotland.shelter.org.uk/empty_homes

² Scottish Government. (2019) Statement in response to climate change emergency. Online from <https://www.gov.scot/publications/global-climate-emergency-scotlands-response-climate-change-secretary-roseanna-cunninghams-statement/>

³ Community Right to Buy. (2019) Information. Online from <https://dtascommunityownership.org.uk/community/community-rights/land-reform-act/community-right-buy>

⁴ Scottish Parliament. (2019) Planning (Scotland) Bill. Online from <https://www.parliament.scot/parliamentarybusiness/Bills/106768.aspx>

⁵ Historic Environment Scotland Policy and Managing Change document portal. (2019) Portal. Online from <https://www.historicenvironment.scot/advice-and-support/planning-and-guidance/legislation-and-guidance/managing-change-in-the-historic-environment-guidance-notes/>

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Scottish Community Development Centre

Formed in 1994, the Scottish Community Development Centre is the lead body for community development in Scotland. We work to our vision of an active, inclusive and just Scotland where our communities are strong, equitable and sustainable. SCDC works with community groups, community development practitioners, government and other policy makers, and local partnerships and agencies to involve communities in their work. SCDC is strongly concerned with tackling poverty and inequality, issues at the heart of community development. The focus of community development is on supporting communities to identify their own priorities, and sustainable development is increasingly a concern of urban communities

How is Scotland doing against this Goal?

The Scottish Government's Chief Statistician found that emissions of air pollutants decreased between 1990 and 2016. However, there was an increase in emissions of ammonia between 2015 and 2016.¹ This is an important issue for people living in Scotland's cities as they are most directly impacted by higher air pollution and missed targets. We know that housing conditions for many in Scotland are inadequate and that this disproportionately affects those on low incomes and who experience poverty. For instance, 50% of all of Scotland's homes have disrepair to critical elements.² SCDC is connected with the work of the Scottish Human Rights Commission, and West Cromwell Street, Persevere & Citadel Courts Residents Association, who have tackled substandard housing and living conditions by using human rights approaches.³ The fact that communities in Scotland have had to use such approaches illustrates that Scotland has considerable distance to travel in terms of ensuring everyone has access to adequate housing.

There are clear links across the SDGs, and we believe that for cities to be sustainable and inclusive, significant effort must be made to reduce poverty. Many of Scotland's most deprived neighbourhoods are in urban areas.⁴ We also know that poverty rates in Scotland continue to rise,⁵ while statistics show that absolute child poverty is decreasing although the rate of decrease has slowed in recent years. Relative child poverty is increasing. There is also a gendered dimension to poverty with particularly high rates of relative poverty for 'lone mothers'.⁶ An important dimension of inclusion in planning is citizen participation. There are welcome moves at a national and local level to increase participation in cities. A notable example of this are current developments in participatory budgeting (PB), with commitments by local authorities to subject 1% of public spending to these approaches.⁷ Evaluation of PB has highlighted a need for this approach to be more inclusive.⁸ In this regard, Glasgow's recent piloting of PB is a positive development, in that it has involved supporting equality groups to take a lead in planning PB processes.⁹

Is Scotland committed to achieving this Goal?

Many of the policy makers we work with appear to have a genuine commitment to sustainability and inclusion. There has been an increasing interest at a policy level in community empowerment and public service reform. Participation and prevention are high on this agenda and are, in our view, integral dimensions of Goal 11. Community involvement and citizen participation are essential to ensure that actions towards meeting Goal 11 are relevant to communities and to ensure longer term attitudinal change and support for the necessary policy changes. However, resources being invested in citizen participation and community empowerment are a fraction of overall government expenditure. Without increased support for, and investment into our communities there is a risk that progress will be uneven, with participation being limited to more affluent and well-organised communities.

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What should Scotland do better to achieve this Goal?

We think that resources need to be redirected towards prevention, partnership and participation. A fairer, more redistributive, tax system is required in order to prevent health inequalities and other problems from emerging 'downstream'.¹⁰ Investment is also required in community development methods to support all groups to participate in making public services more sustainable and effective. Community development works with groups to support them to have more influence over decisions affecting their lives and their communities. It supports groups who are under-represented in democratic structures at all levels to participate. This includes, but is not limited to, younger people, women, ethnic minorities, LGBTQ communities, disabled people, and people experiencing poverty and disadvantage. If this support is in place, innovative approaches to participation and empowerment can be fully realised (e.g. PB, the Community Empowerment (Scotland) Act¹¹ and the newly proposed citizens' assembly¹²).

We believe that communities need to be able to take a lead on issues of sustainability – again, because this ensures actions are relevant to, and supported by, the people they impact the most. However, community involvement is hampered by the fact that Scotland has the largest average population per basic unit of local government of any developed country. This means that each elected representative in Scotland has to represent more people than elected representatives in other developed countries do, with all the consequences for the quality of representation. Scotland should learn from how local democracy works in other European countries by creating more local democratic structures that enable people to influence decisions that affect their communities, including around issues of sustainability. The current Scottish Government Local Governance Review offers an opportunity to devolve power to the local level. There are different options available, including strengthening community councils (and making them more democratic)¹³ and creating new ways for communities and community organisations to have more power at a local level.

Case study — city planning and its impact on under-represented groups

In developing our response to the SDG 'snapshot review', SCDC invited its network of individuals and organisations active in the field of community development to give their view.

An example was provided of how policy in relation to sustainable cities has a direct impact on women. We have broadened this out to cover other under-represented groups. Even well-intentioned city planning and citizen participation processes can have a negative impact on already under-represented groups. If these groups are not able to participate, or face barriers to participation, there is a risk that planning and decision-making about spaces, streets, and green areas will not reflect the needs and priorities of these groups. This can ultimately prevent people from being able to live in cities, working entirely against Goal 11's aims. On the other hand, if the perspectives of currently under-represented groups are taken into account within urban planning decisions, cities will become more inclusive and sustainable for everyone.

Author

Andrew Paterson, Policy and Research Officer at the Scottish Community Development Centre

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² Scottish Government. (2018) Scottish House Condition Survey: 2017 Key Findings. Online from <https://www.gov.scot/publications/scottish-house-condition-survey-2017-key-findings>

³ Scottish Human Rights Commission. (date unknown) Right to Housing. Online from <http://www.scottishhumanrights.com/economic-social-cultural-rights/housing>

⁴ Scottish Government. (2016) Scottish Index of Multiple Deprivation 2016. Online from <https://simd.scot/>

⁵ Scottish Government. (2019) Poverty and income inequality in Scotland: 2015-2018. Online from <https://www.gov.scot/publications/poverty-income-inequality-scotland-2015-18/>

⁶ Scottish Government. (2019) Gender and Poverty. Poverty and income inequality in Scotland: 2015-2018. Online from <https://www.gov.scot/publications/poverty-income-inequality-scotland-2015-18/pages/7/>

⁷ PB Scotland. (2017) '1% local government target sees £100 million for PB'. PB Scotland website. Online from <https://pbscotland.scot/blog/2017/10/30/1-local-government-goal-sees-100-million-for-pb-in-communities>

⁸ O'Hagan, A., O'Conner, C.H., MacRae, C., Broadhurst, J. and Teedon, P. (2017) Evaluating Participatory Budgeting Activity in Scotland – Interim Report Year 2. Online from <https://pbscotland.scot/blog/2017/11/10/interim-evaluation-report-on-pb-in-scotland>

⁹ PB Scotland. (2018) 'Glasgow's PB journey detailed in new report' PB Scotland website. Online from <https://pbscotland.scot/blog/2018/10/10/glasgows-pb-journey-detailed-in-new-report?rq=glasgow>

¹⁰ NHS Health Scotland. (2019) Income inequality. NHS Health Scotland. Online from <http://www.healthscotland.scot/health-inequalities/fundamental-causes/income-inequality/tax>

¹¹ Communities Channel Scotland. (2019) Community Empowerment Bill. Online from <http://www.communityscot.org.uk/resources/policy-developments/community-empowerment-bill/>

¹² The Herald. (2019) 'Nicola Sturgeon wants to set up a Citizens' Assembly. But what is that?'. Online from <https://www.heraldscotland.com/news/17595139.nicola-sturgeon-wants-to-set-up-a-citizens-assembly-but-what-is-that/>

¹³ Paterson, A., Nelis, P. Escobar, O. (2019) Strengthening Community Councils: Exploring how community councils can contribute to democratic renewal in Scotland. Scottish Community Development Centre and What Works Scotland. Online from <https://www.scdc.org.uk/what/strengthening-community-councils>

Ensure sustainable consumption and production patterns

The James Hutton Institute

The James Hutton Institute (JHI) combines research strengths in crops, soils and land use with environmental research, and makes a major contribution to the understanding of key global issues, such as food, energy and environmental security, and develops and promotes effective technological and management solutions to these. As part of this JHI's research portfolio delivers to many of the SDGs and in particular to SDG 12. This is done through engagement with major (and minor) stakeholders in the area of agri-food.

How is Scotland doing against this Goal?

SDG 12, Responsible Consumption and Production, encompasses a wide range of issues including materials recycling, procurement practices, product labelling and sustainable sourcing. The focus of our contribution is on agri-food. Scotland can be considered a leader in this area of SDG 12 and its emphasis on 'sustainable consumption and production patterns'. Via the links between the organisations that constitute the Scottish Environment, Food and Agriculture Research Institutes,¹ the full supply and value chains from farm-to-fork/seed-to-sewage are covered. Crucially, the research undertaken by the James Hutton Institute is informed by stakeholders and co-constructed with them.

This research, underpinned by Scottish Government funding, and its seamless translation to stakeholders has seen Scotland significantly improve its agriculture and hence responsible production. Also, research in the areas of health, food waste and food innovation are all delivering wins regarding responsible consumption by identifying healthier options for the consumer, best practises for storage. and options for processors to ensure the product stays fresher longer.

The targets we are focussing on in our research are the basal primary foods including potato, cereals, soft fruit and vegetables. Allied to this is innovation in food processing, safety across the supply and value chains, and food waste. These efforts are delivering information to be exploited by all, such as improved nutritive and health beneficial value in these crops, new processing approaches to increase dietary fibre, and models and processes to reduce the incidence of food poisoning.

At the food waste level, stakeholder engagement is identifying the behaviours leading to food waste and routes to their diminishment and change. In addition, significant steps are being made to valorise where reduction is difficult. For example, while in primary agriculture there is always waste, these crops can be a source of sustainable food ingredients with simple food-safe processing.

Scientists at the James Hutton Institute see the SDGs as goals to strive towards and view these at a geographic or regional level to measure successful impact. We feel that Scotland is definitely on track to deliver on many of the SDG 12 Targets such as sustainable management and efficient use of natural resources, substantially reducing waste generation and food losses along production and supply chains, including post-harvest losses. In addition, this is all delivered within a framework of interaction with stakeholders to increase awareness and to facilitate sustainable development and lifestyles in harmony with nature.

Is Scotland committed to achieving this Goal?

Scotland is a land of dichotomies: fantastic produce, but terrible health related to multiple factors including dietary behaviours. It produces some of the world's best shellfish, but

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more than 95% of it is exported to Mediterranean countries. Scotland's most prolific crop, barley, besides being the base ingredient for the water of life (whisky), also can be the basis of many very nutritious and health promoting foods. However, besides soup very little is done with it. All that being said, there needs to be a solid political and governmental commitment to continued support for Scotland's responsible production and consumption of food. This could take the form of both support mechanisms (funding, advice, knowledge hubs, demonstration platforms) and legislation against irresponsible behaviours. Food is a major industry in Scotland. The food industry, via the Scottish Government, support the industry group Scotland Food and Drink, and have realised that they need to pull together to realise their ambition to double the turnover in farming, fishing, and food and drink to £30 billion by 2030.² This national approach is driven by the desire to be 'champions of responsible and sustainable production' and 'change behaviours around food and drink consumption'.³ The James Hutton Institute has the pleasure of being part of this national process dealing with innovations to deliver these aims.

What should Scotland do better to achieve this Goal?

Scotland's national views on responsible production and consumption are not the same. There is a contradiction between how many people in Scotland see their food and what they actually consume. Consumers outside Scotland see it as a land of clean and sustainable food production, yet many Scots have a poor diet which barely reflects this view.

The Scottish and UK governmental diet and health plans have struggled to make significant impacts over the last 20 to 30 years.⁴ Perhaps Scotland needs to adopt another model to achieve the Goal and thereby create impact. Taking the example of Finland and the Karelian region as a model – here, an appalling cardio-vascular disease record prevailed in the early 1970s. A comprehensive community-based intervention involving health services, NGOs, academia, industry, media and public policy was undertaken to deliver major health benefits. Crucially, this was led by a 'health czar' whose term of office spanned several governments, thus allowing for continuity. The current and future political situation is Scotland could see such an approach work, but with a target on responsible production and consumption. Engagement across and within the food and drink sector across discovery, innovation and exploitation is working well but could be delivered better through better government support. Where food and drink are considered, governments tend to knee-jerk into legislation rather than 'offer carrots' for evolutionary change. The establishment of an industry/academia/non-governmental organisation funding scheme delivering to the Targets of SDG 12 would make sense and deliver outputs beneficial to all.

Additionally, an annual prize for the delivery on the SDGs would highlight that Scotland and its population are taking these seriously. The prize should be through nomination, not self-selecting, to engender a spirit of cross-sectoral trust and buy-in.

Case study – food waste in a circular economy

In 2017, the Circular Economy award programme (an initiative of the World Economic Forum and the Forum of Young Global Leaders, run in collaboration with Accenture Strategy) gave the Scottish Government the award in the category of Governments, Cities and Regions for its circular economy policy and actions. Dealing with food waste is implicit in circular economy activities. I have overseen work which sought to understand what behaviours lead to food waste at the consumer and industry levels.⁵ The conclusions of this work have informed what Zero Waste Scotland will do going forward to change consumer behaviours to reduce food waste. At the primary production level we will always have food waste which

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can be utilised and exploited for other means. This means that we absolutely need to view the SDGs together and not as isolated aims. For food waste, the Institute has undertaken several studies looking at the conversion of food waste into new valuable products, often potentially replacing the current ones generated through unsustainable fossil fuel driven processes. For example, the Institute has delivered a portfolio of projects converting waste into products for cereals (food ingredients and sustainable chemicals feedstocks), potato haulms (sources of bioactive potentially CVD therapeutic natural chemicals), and soft fruit (sustainable colourants, antioxidants and biodegradable microbeads for the cosmetics industry as plastic replacements). It is important to note that these approaches also deliver to the SDG 11, Sustainable Cities and Communities, and to SDG 12, Responsible Consumption and Production.

Author

Professor Derek Stewart, AgriFood Business Sector Lead at The James Hutton Institute.

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³ Withers, James. (2018) Ambitions 2030: Online from <https://foodanddrink.scot/media/1465/ambition-2030.pdf>

⁴ See e.g. The Scottish Government. (2018) A healthier future: Scotland's diet and healthy weight delivery plan. Online from <https://www.gov.scot/publications/healthier-future-scotlands-diet-healthy-weight-delivery-plan/>

⁵ Toma, Luiz; Font, Montserrat Costa; and Thompson, Bethan. (2017) Impact of consumers' understanding of date labelling on food waste behaviour. Operational Research, pp.1-18. Online from <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s12351-017-0352-3>

Take urgent action to combat climate change and its impacts

Stop Climate Chaos Scotland

Stop Climate Chaos Scotland is a diverse coalition of over 40 Scottish civil society organisations, campaigning together on climate change. Our members include environment, faith and belief groups, international development organisations, trade and student unions, and community groups. Our focus is on climate change mitigation. We believe the Scottish Government should take bold action to tackle climate change and that Scotland should deliver its fair share of action in response to SDG Goal 13 and the Paris Agreement and in supporting climate justice around the world. We are currently campaigning for an ambitious new Climate Change Bill for Scotland.

How is Scotland doing against this Goal?

It is ten years since the Climate Change Act was passed by the Scottish Parliament, and recent science has shown the devastating consequences facing a world which carries on with business as usual. In October 2018, a Special Report from the UN's Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) painted a bleak picture of far-reaching and damaging impacts for people, places and nature if global warming exceeds 1.5°C. The impacts of climate change are already being faced by those least responsible and most vulnerable. The difference in limiting climate change to 1.5°C compared to allowing warming to reach 2°C cannot be overstated. Warming of 2°C would have even more devastating and irreversible impacts including:

- 60 million more urban residents exposed to severe drought by 2100;
- An additional 2bn people worldwide exposed to extreme heat waves at least once every 20 years;
- The Arctic will be ice-free at least once every 10 years, rather than once every 100 years, with far-reaching consequences for arctic wildlife;
- Virtually all coral reefs are lost by 2100, due to bleaching, whereas 1.5°C means we keep up to 30% of today's coral reefs.

Scotland must do its part to limit warming to 1.5°C. This requires a rapid acceleration of action over the next decade. While there has been strong progress in Scotland so far, it is now time to ramp this up to ensure Scotland is responding to the demands of science. In 2009, the Scottish Parliament unanimously passed the Climate Change Act and its demanding, ambitious and legally binding targets. Since then, Scotland has made strong progress in taking action to combat climate change. Domestic emissions have fallen by 45% from 1990 baseline levels. There has been significant progress in some sectors, including the decarbonising of energy supply, notably with the 2016 closure of the last coal-fired power station in Longannet, and also with regard to waste management. Nevertheless, there is plenty more opportunity in other sectors. This includes transport and agriculture, where emissions have fallen less than 1% and 4%, respectively, since 1990. To truly deliver the urgent action required for Goal 13, more action across all sectors is needed.

Take urgent action to combat climate change and its impacts

Figure 1: Change in Net Emissions by Scottish Government Sector Between 1990 and 2016 – in MtCO₂e, and percentage changes¹

Is Scotland committed to achieving this Goal?

The current political and policy commitments do not stack up to the levels of urgent action we need to see over the next decade. In May 2018, the Scottish Government introduced a new Climate Change Bill to the Scottish Parliament which contained no new policies or measures to tackle emissions, failing to meet the ‘far-reaching and rapid’ action called for by the IPCC last year. The Climate Change Bill is still working its way through the Scottish Parliament, with parties now at the stage of proposing amendments. In May 2019, the UK Committee on Climate Change advised that Scotland can and should set a target to reach net-zero greenhouse gas emissions, the point at which more emissions are absorbed through offsetting techniques like forestry than are being emitted, by 2045 at the latest.

Responding immediately, the Scottish Government announced they would lodge their own amendment to support this target in the new Climate Change Bill. Setting a target for net-zero emissions by 2045 is an exciting improvement to our climate ambition that sets the right destination for Scotland in the long term. It is also important to note that the Scottish Parliament has been active in promoting support for climate adaptation overseas. Through its Climate Justice Fund, the Scottish Government has funded a number of projects in developing countries to help communities adapt to the effects of climate change. The Scottish Government’s commitment of £3m per year to this fund is very welcome, especially as international development is a reserved matter for the UK Government.

What should Scotland do better to achieve this Goal?

Attention in Scotland must turn to creating new policy measures needed to cut emissions urgently over the next decade, particularly in sectors where little progress has been made so far, such as energy efficiency, agriculture, and transport. Policies in these areas can be positively transformative for people’s lives in Scotland with warmer, more efficient home heating, a flourishing countryside, and an improved public and active travel network

Take urgent action to combat climate change and its impacts

cleaning up our air all while reducing emissions. In terms of support for achieving SDG 13 globally, the Scottish Government should focus more on the international context of its policy decisions at home. Achieving this goal requires policy coherence with global climate policy, and efforts to ensure that domestic policies do not undermine international efforts. Scotland could pioneer parliamentary or policy mechanisms which ensure policy coherence and which scrutinise policies that contradict domestic and international climate policy commitments.

Author

Ryan Morrison, Campaigns Officer at Stop Climate Chaos Scotland

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Conserve and sustainably use the oceans, seas and marine resources for sustainable development

Marine Conservation Society

The Marine Conservation Society (MCS) campaigns for clean seas and beaches, sustainable fisheries, and protection of marine life. Through education, community involvement and collaboration, MCS raises awareness of the threats that face our seas and promotes individual, industry, and government action to protect the marine environment. MCS provides guidance on marine conservation, including the annual Good Beach Guide and the Good Fish Guide as well as involving thousands of volunteers in projects and surveys such as MCS Beachwatch. MCS has run a dedicated Scotland programme since April 2000.

How is Scotland doing against this Goal?

Scotland has made some progress toward Goal 14, although the picture is mixed. Much of the legal and policy framework is to be welcomed and is indeed world-class on paper. In many cases it delivers welcome and tangible marine conservation successes. However, in other cases the gap between rhetoric and reality remains as concrete measures are awaited. The Marine (Scotland) Act 2010¹ provides a potentially world-leading legal framework with, inter alia, duties on Scottish Ministers to further sustainable development, including the protection and, where appropriate, enhancement of the health of the Scottish marine area, to deliver a National Marine Plan (NMP)² that includes marine ecosystem objectives, published in 2015, and to establish a network of Marine Protected Areas (MPA).³ There is much in the NMP that could contribute to ecosystem resilience in principle. For example, a general policy in the NMP was crucial to trigger proposals to improve protection for vulnerable Priority Marine Features (PMFs) outside the MPA network, following scallop dredger damage to a flameshell bed in outer Loch Carron. New protection measures are, however, still awaited. Whilst there is much to welcome with the NMP on paper, there has been only limited progress in developing regional marine plans that would actually deliver sustainable management and ecosystem enhancement in practice. A 2017 review of the Plan found that 'it was acknowledged that it will not be until the Scottish Marine Regions (SMRs) are rolled out that the marine planning framework will fully deliver'.⁴ Tensions also exist in the plan between sectoral policies on oil and gas extraction and climate change targets, and between committing to sustainable development whilst providing in-principle support of unsustainable aquaculture industry growth targets.

Scotland's Marine Protected Area (MPA) network is developing and already exceeds 10% of the Scottish marine area. However, there have been delays in establishing further sites needed to contribute to network coherence, although a further four sites have recently gone to public consultation. Whilst all sites are legally protected from activities other than fishing through the licensing process, there is some contention about the degree to which inshore sites are adequately protected from some licensed activities such as aquaculture. Also, much of the network, particularly offshore, still awaits essential statutory measures to provide protection from damaging fishing activity. A tranche of management for the most vulnerable inshore MPAs provided protection for over 2,200km² of inshore waters from damaging bottom-trawling and mechanical dredging in 2016. These were progressive, ecosystem-based conservation measures rather than blanket bans throughout all sites. However, there is some frustration with delays in delivering statutory fisheries protection measures for the remaining inshore sites (a matter within the devolved competence of the Scottish Government) and for the large offshore sites that still require fisheries protection measures agreed by relevant EU member states through the Common Fisheries Policy (CFP).

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On fishing, Scotland has shown leadership offshore, with initiatives such as the cod recovery plan. However, there are great concerns about the discarding of unwanted fish, particularly of 'choke' species across a number of fisheries in Scotland and the UK. Under the CFP, the landing obligation is a vital tool to eliminate the wasteful practice of discarding, reduce human impact on marine ecosystems, and restore fish stocks to sustainable levels. However, there are serious concerns that in Scotland and throughout the UK, the landing obligation is not being properly implemented and enforced.⁵ The result is that stocks are being subjected to increased fishing mortality with a real risk of overfishing. This must be addressed as a matter of urgency to prevent seriously harming our fisheries resources and the wider marine environment on which our fishing industry and coastal communities depend. In the northeast Atlantic, 43% of assessed fish stocks were subject to overfishing in 2016⁶ and there remain many more fish and shellfish stocks that are not sufficiently assessed to know if overfishing is occurring.⁷ In addition, there is believed to be widespread non-compliance with the EU landing obligation which could result in an increase in fishing mortality and even further overfishing. Inshore, the 2015 publication of an Inshore Fisheries Strategy⁸ was welcome. But a promised commitment to introduce an Inshore Fisheries Bill, urgently needed to provide spatial management, address gear conflict and deliver ecosystem-based fisheries management, has been delayed. It has been frustrating that progress has been somewhat slowed as a result of Scotland preparing for all eventualities following the referendum on membership in the EU. However, the Future of Fisheries Management⁹ stakeholder discussion process in Scotland must be taken as an opportunity for a complete re-think. This should result in proposals for fresh legislation that delivers modernised and sustainable fisheries management which enhances the marine biodiversity of which these fish and shellfish stocks are part and parcel, and upon which their health depends.

On marine pollution, Scotland was the first nation in the UK to establish a Marine Litter Strategy and Action Plan,¹⁰ to commit to banning plastic-stemmed cotton-buds, and to commit to designing a return-to-retail deposit return scheme for plastic and glass bottles and aluminium cans. Along with Scotland's legislation to ban production and sale of rinse-off products containing plastic microbeads, which has tougher penalties than elsewhere in the UK, these are welcome and progressive initiatives. But progress has been slower than anticipated when the strategy was established in 2010. More recent commitments to meet requirements of EU Directives on single-use plastics and to progress work on tackling sources of marine litter are welcome but need continued commitment and funding. The recent UK Marine Strategy report¹¹ starkly highlights that we are overshooting the environmental limits of our seas. To date, the UK administrations, including the Scottish Government, reported meeting only four out of 15 indicators of Good Environmental Status (GES, see below).

Is Scotland committed to achieving this Goal?

There is strong political and policy commitment to achieving SDG 14 in Scotland. Most recently this was evidenced by Scotland showing leadership on measures to tackle ocean plastics and other forms of marine pollution, rapidly putting in place an emergency Marine Protected Area to protect flammeshell beds in Loch Carron following damage by a rogue scallop dredger in 2017 (recently made permanent), setting out proposals to modernise fishing in Scotland, committing to complete Scotland's MPA network and, prompted by the Loch Carron incident, to improve protection for vulnerable Priority Marine Features in wider seas beyond the MPA network. However, in some instances there is still a sizeable gap between rhetoric and reality, and there are fundamental contradictions in policy such

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as those highlighted in the National Marine Plan regarding the expansion of the aquaculture and oil and gas sectors. In response to the Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services (IPBES) Global Assessment in April 2019, Scotland's First Minister Nicola Sturgeon said 'the protection of our natural environment is such a priority that, just as on climate change, the obligation on all of us is to look afresh at everything that we are doing and make a decision [...]. As we have done on climate change, we need to raise the bar of global leadership and make sure that we are continuing to get much higher over the bar than anybody else.'¹² This recognition of the crisis facing our natural world, including life below water, is welcome, but a complete re-think is needed of how to do business at and around the sea. Published in 2011, Scotland's Marine Atlas highlighted the many concerns and declines facing Scotland's marine environment, seabird populations, shark, skate and ray populations, harbour seals and sedimentary and deepwater seabed habitats in particular.¹³ Almost nine years on, despite some of the welcome progress discussed, the aforementioned UK Marine Strategy underlines that we are overshooting the environmental limits of our seas. It reveals that to date the UK administrations, including the Scottish Government, have reported meeting only four out of 15 indicators of good environmental status and will fail to meet targets, including for the health of seabirds, fish, benthic habitats, non-indigenous species, commercial fish and shellfish and marine litter, by 2020. Whilst the trends are either stable or increasing for 10 of the 11 indicators, five of these are from a baseline of failing to meet the target (fish, benthic habitats, non-indigenous species, commercial fish and shellfish and marine litter) and there is a worrying downward trend in seabird status from an already failed target.

Even of the four where good environmental status has been deemed to be met, there are issues, since the 'contaminants' indicator that has a green rating does not take account of microplastic contamination. Despite this failure and the recent dire warning of biodiversity decline on land and sea by the IPBES, this key UK framework, which aims to help ensure marine ecosystems recover to a healthy condition, is worryingly weak.

What should Scotland do better to achieve this Goal?

If we are truly to live within environmental limits, the health of our marine ecosystems has to be front and centre of decision-making, where commitment is made to protect remaining ecosystems that are in good condition and to restore degraded ecosystems on a large-scale. On land, this thinking is widespread through recognition of the need to restore peatlands and commit to replanting forests on a landscape scale. Similar thinking is needed for life below water, both 'passive' restoration by removing pressure from our marine environment, and 'active' restoration in the form of habitat recreation/rewilding projects such as replanting seagrass beds, managed coastal realignment, and the reintroduction of reef-forming organisms such as native oysters. With the acknowledged climate emergency, the restoration of 'blue carbon' stores can contribute toward mitigating and adapting to climate change by making our oceans more resilient to change. Without a step-change in approach we risk losing not only iconic nature, but also the ecosystem service benefits that a healthy marine environment provides for people, including food, energy, recreation, and a sense of wellbeing. To achieve such a step-change we need to greatly strengthen the UK marine strategy to deliver large-scale ecosystem protection and enhancement; implement the Marine (Scotland) Act 2010 and Marine and Coastal Access Act 2009 in full, including completing the network of MPAs and ensuring they are properly protected and developing marine plans that proactively drive enhancement of underwater ecosystems; deliver robust, effective strategies for highly mobile species (seabirds and cetaceans); ensure developing UK fisheries legislation and future Scottish fisheries legislation enables

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effective ecosystem-based fisheries management through spatial measures, gear separation and effort control and includes legal commitments to fish within sustainable limits; end the practice of discards by meeting the landing obligation in full; substantially increase investment in marine science (including the MPA monitoring strategy), marine planning, marine governance, fisheries management and compliance, including fully documented fisheries, and ecosystem monitoring; drive down single-use plastic, prevent plastic from 'leaking' into the sea, and deliver a zero waste future through new Circular Economy legislation and full implementation of the marine litter strategy; accelerate a just transition to a zero carbon future in response to the climate emergency; include statutory ecological targets for restoring nature's blue carbon habitats, including seagrass beds and living reefs, in new climate change legislation and prevent any activities such as deep-sea mining that would irreversibly damage fragile marine ecosystems from starting up in Scotland in future.

Case study — seafloor integrity research

The Marine Conservation Society coordinate the underwater citizen science diving project Seasearch, where divers record seabed life and human impact on it. Our experience of seeing first-hand both the amazing life on the seabed out of sight and out of mind to most, and the impact on it from anthropogenic activity, and particularly the impact of heavy bottom-towed fishing gears, underpins our calls for sustainable fishing that maintains and enhances the health of the seafloor. Under the UK Marine strategy, Scotland, along with all UK nations, is required to ensure our seafloor is healthy by safeguarding its structure and the wildlife that call it home. The official term for this is 'Seafloor Integrity', a term which reflects the complex inter-relationship between the geology of the seafloor, the species that live on and in the seabed and interactions with the wider marine environment. The seafloor provides refuge and nursery areas for fish, shellfish and other invertebrate species which, if damaged or disturbed, can impact other fish and shellfish species, seabirds and marine mammals that rely on them. If our seafloors are healthy they should be home to flourishing sealife, able to support the food chain, store carbon, deliver nutrient cycling services and support sustainable activity, including fishing, recreation (such as diving and sea-angling), and space for appropriately located offshore developments.

The UK Government's latest assessment of progress revealed that Good Environmental Status for Seafloor Integrity will not be met by 2020. Scotland's Marine Atlas highlighted that, along with climate change, fishing is the most widespread pressure on our seas and that the status of most of the seabed was of 'some' or 'many' concerns. The UK Marine Strategy consultation document states that 'in 2012, the consensus amongst experts was that the spatial extent of damage to the seabed from fishing gear was greater than any damage caused by other activities'. At the same time the IPBES report stated that 'in marine systems, fishing has had the most impact on biodiversity (target species, non-target species and habitats) in the past 50 years alongside other significant drivers'. To improve our understanding of the impacts of bottom-towed fishing on the seafloor, Scottish Environment LINK, for which MCS convenes the Marine Group, commissioned an independent report to inform how far current and anticipated fisheries management measures in Scotland would contribute to meeting seafloor integrity targets. The report concluded that the seafloor is likely to be so far modified from its natural state that it would be hard to know what its natural state once was. Instead, the critical test would be the ability of the seafloor to recover, and use of the seabed should only progress once the recovery rate and, crucially, potential is known. To test sustainability and seafloor recovery, the report recommended the use of Scotland's new nature conservation MPAs and

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establishment of further demonstration and research MPAs, underlining the importance of a suitably resourced MPA monitoring strategy. As Good Environmental Status for Seafloor Integrity across UK seafloors has not been met, the UK Marine Strategy must be revised to ensure it is as ambitious as possible. This should include clear assessments of the sustainability of activities that can impact seafloor integrity, particularly the use of mobile fishing gear, and follow the increasing weight of scientific evidence that requires a precautionary approach for managing and protecting the seafloor.

Further reading

Scottish Environment LINK publications and commissioned reports supporting advocacy for the Marine (Scotland) Act 2010, new Marine Protected Areas and marine ecosystem recovery:

- <http://www.scotlink.org/files/publication/LINKReports/LINKmtfReportFindingNIMAs.pdf>
- <http://www.scotlink.org/wp/files/documents/SAMS-Report-with-LINK-Foreword.pdf>
- http://www.scotlink.org/files/publication/LINKReports/SAMSReportManagingMPAs_full.pdf
- [http://www.scotlink.org/files/publication/LINKReports/Valuing_the_benefits_MPA_Network_Scotland_Report_\(final\).pdf](http://www.scotlink.org/files/publication/LINKReports/Valuing_the_benefits_MPA_Network_Scotland_Report_(final).pdf)
- http://www.scotlink.org/wp/files/documents/SEL_SeafloorIntegrity_Report_A4_March19-1.pdf

Author

Calum Duncan, Head of Conservation Scotland for the Marine Conservation Society

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² Scottish Government. (2015) National Marine Plan. Online from <https://www.gov.scot/publications/scotlands-national-marine-plan/>

³ Scottish Government. (2019) Scotland's Marine Protected Areas. Online from <https://www2.gov.scot/Topics/marine/marine-environment/mpanetwork>

⁴ Scottish Coastal Forum. (2018) Workshop on National Marine Plan. Online from <https://www2.gov.scot/Topics/marine/seamanagement/national/SCFReviewWorkshop>

⁵ Marine Conservation Society. (2019) Urgent recommendations for landing obligation. Online from <https://www.mcsuk.org/media/urgent-recommendations-for-landing-obligation-in-2019.pdf>

⁶ European Commission. (2018). Working document Accompanying the document Communication from the Commission on the State of Play of the Common Fisheries Policy and Consultation on the Fishing Opportunities for 2019. Online from <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=SWD:2018:329:FIN>

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⁸ Scottish Government. (2015) Inshore Fisheries Strategy. Online from <https://www2.gov.scot/Topics/marine/Sea-Fisheries/InshoreFisheries/InshoreFisheriesStrategy>

⁹ Scottish Government. (2019) Future of Fisheries Management discussion paper. Online from <https://www.gov.scot/publications/national-discussion-paper-future-fisheries-management-scotland>

¹⁰ Scottish Government. (2014) Scotland's Marine Litter Strategy. Online from <https://www.gov.scot/publications/marine-litter-strategy-scotland/>

¹¹ DEFRA. (2019) UK Marine Strategy report. Online from https://consult.defra.gov.uk/marine/updated-uk-marine-strategy-part-one/supporting_documents/UKmarinestrategypart1consultdocumentfinal.pdf

¹² Scottish Parliament. (2019) Meeting of the Parliament, 9 May 2019. Online from <http://www.parliament.scot/parliamentarybusiness/report.aspx?r=12083&i=109359&c=2173440>

¹³ Scottish Government. (2011) Scotland's Marine Atlas. Online from <https://www2.gov.scot/Publications/2011/03/16182005/0>

Protect, restore and promote sustainable use of terrestrial ecosystems, sustainably manage forests, combat desertification, and halt and reverse land degradation and halt biodiversity loss

Scottish Wildlife Trust

The Scottish Wildlife Trust champions the cause of wildlife through policy and campaigning work, demonstrates best practice through practical conservation and innovative partnerships, and inspires people to take positive action through its education and engagement activities. It manages a network of 120 wildlife reserves across Scotland and is a member of the UK-wide Wildlife Trusts movement.

How is Scotland doing against this Goal?

Scottish Natural Heritage's 2016 interim report on Scotland's progress towards the binding Aichi Biodiversity Targets, set by the UN Convention on Biological Diversity, outlines that 'Scotland's biodiversity indicators, the condition of notified habitats and species on protected areas, and progress towards meeting Scotland's biodiversity targets demonstrated that biodiversity loss had not yet been halted and would require renewed and sustained effort over a longer period.'¹ In the wider context, the latest Living Planet Report highlights that most of the Aichi targets are unlikely to be met, while 'the main drivers of biodiversity decline continue to be the overexploitation of species, agriculture and land conversion'.² Scotland's ecological footprint³ already exceeds 'three-planet living', as recognised recently by the Scottish Environmental Protection Agency (SEPA). Reducing our ecological footprint nationally and internationally is essential for any long-term viability of the economy. In particular, 'one-planet prosperity',⁴ requires an urgent, systemic transition in our food production. Steffen's et al Planetary Boundaries framework⁵ shows that biodiversity and the biogeochemical flows of nitrogen and phosphorus are the three highest-risk boundaries globally – these boundaries have already been crossed. Land-system and climate change are close behind. The intensification and production-focus of our agricultural systems are key, often determining, factors in all of these risks. Steffen et al identify climate change and biosphere integrity (what is typically biodiversity) as 'core boundaries' whose crossing would 'drive the Earth System into a new state'.⁶

While Scotland's agricultural greenhouse gas emissions have declined since the 1990s, these declines 'are often associated with reduced production rather than increased efficiency',⁷ and agricultural systems continue to contribute over a quarter of Scotland's emissions – the second largest contributor nationally. Scotland's biodiversity is in net decline. We have seen some important progress, such as legal protection for beavers who are now well-placed to continue transforming aspects of Scotland's ecosystems for the better. But these should not obscure the fact that Scotland's life on land remains threatened by human action and actively pursued policies.

Is Scotland committed to achieving this Goal?

There is a yawning gap between political commitments and firm actions. Overall, the implementation gap between rhetoric, and even published stated strategy, and what we see on the ground in terms of coordination and integration is widening. In comparison, the Welsh Assembly have put into legislation what the Scottish Government will only put into policy aims. There is therefore less accountability and resilience against changes to policy that could impact on the delivery of Goal 15. The Land Use Strategy from 2014, which is generally regarded as an excellent framework, could be doing much more than it currently is. Adopting a 'total ecosystem approach', the Strategy aimed to integrate policy development and implementation across land use. But it is rare that the Strategy is used in this way by government, despite its potential. That has put conservation organisations in the strange position of advocating for the Scottish Government to give

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appropriate attention to its own strategy.

Forestry is another key area where more needs to be done, not least to help deliver net-zero emissions by 2045 at the latest. The Scottish Government's new Forestry Strategy has been highly criticised for not going far enough, and the UK Forestry Strategy itself, which forms its basis, is in need of a refresh. It is worth noting the 21% figure for total land cover (substantially below the European average) in the new strategy is actually reduced from the previous strategy's goal of 25%, while annual targets working towards it have failed to be met every year so far. The worry is that we may view the poor UK performance as the baseline to judge Scotland's performance which is just a little less poor. The issue of habitat fragmentation is also not addressed substantively by the Strategy.

Overall, rhetorical commitments and strategies are numerous, and often promising. But it is rare that we see substantial follow-through on those – genuine commitment to marshalling and coordinating resources to tackle substantial declines in life on land remains particularly elusive.

What should Scotland do better to achieve this Goal?

Our livestock, crops, soil, and forestry can be interlinked. Agroecological systems favour the use of integrated methods to deliver wide-ranging benefits in soil functionality, limiting fertiliser use, reducing run-off, sequestering carbon, and restoring biodiversity, in addition to protecting wildlife for its own sake. We already have examples where agricultural practices are contributing to ecosystem health, but their viability is under threat. As the 2016 State of Nature (Scotland) report outlines

'the High Nature Value (HNV) farming and crofting of agriculturally marginal lands in the Highlands, islands and uplands of Scotland is increasingly difficult to sustain economically and socially. However, the sensitive grazing regimes and low-intensity arable production involved are hugely valuable for a whole suite of wildlife, and subsidies directed to HNV farming systems deliver tangible environmental benefits from public investment'.⁸

Rewarding responsible land managers for providing local and dispersed public goods can help increase the economic viability of HNV farming systems. As the UK leaves the EU, leaving the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) is a chance to rewrite the rules that govern farm support. Rather than simply rewarding farmers for producing food, we need to ensure that public money goes to supporting environmental and social public goods in order to produce healthy, sustainable food without negatively impacting the ecological processes we rely on. Farmers often work on extremely tight margins. We need to tackle the market failures that skew our valuation of food and its dependency on healthy ecosystems. Cheap food is only possible because we degrade our ecosystems and allow supermarket competition to continually narrow producer margins: high antibiotic use, biodiversity decline, reduced soil functionality, and diet-related illnesses are the real price we have paid for cheap food. Most of the money spent under the CAP has reinforced this system by favouring production. By accounting not just for these negatives, but also for the positives that come from agroecological approaches, a replacement policy can make public money deliver plentiful, quality food at a price that is affordable. Farmers, foresters, and land managers play an important role in engaging people with the environment through, for example, supporting public access to their land and hosting educational visits. This is crucial in raising awareness and understanding of nature and wildlife, our land and our food

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systems, but also in helping people to care about these aspects which may otherwise be far from their daily experience. This activity needs investment which, as well as contributing to a healthier society, can also promote sustainable rural communities through tourism.

Case study — development versus protection

Given the policy areas highlighted above, the Coul Links case provides a useful, specific case where developmental pressures interact with local protections. Coul Link is a stretch of land in East Sutherland under threat from the development of an 18-hole golf course, despite being protected by three designations: a Site of Special Scientific Interest (SSSI), a Special Conservation Area (SPA), and as a Ramsar Site. This demonstrates the national and international importance of this place for wildlife. The Scottish Wildlife Trust previously managed the area until the landowner decided not to renew the contract. Home to rare and endangered wildlife, the area is one of the few places of its kind to remain relatively undisturbed by development. Being a Ramsar site – a global convention protecting wetlands – the area is of particular relevance to Goal 15 (Target 15.1 and Indicator 15.1.2), though a clearer indicator is found in Goal 6, (Indicator 6.6.1). While Scotland has pledged to lead by example on the Goals, internationally and nationally designated Scottish wetlands are threatened. The recent planning note from the Scottish Government on the status given to Ramsar sites, according to a Government spokesperson, was issued with Coul Links in mind. The note implies a level of protection below that of the rest of the UK where Ramsar sites enjoy Natura 2000 level protections by default in all cases – a position that contradicts earlier assurances given by Government. This is a specific example of where Goal 15 has not been given sufficient weight in planning. It could easily be rectified to better reflect the Scottish Government’s commitments and responsibilities by clarifying that Ramsar Sites enjoy Natura 2000 levels of protection, and by committing to prioritise the social, environmental, and economic benefits that come from protecting biodiversity.

The golf course proposals at Coul Links may yet be thrown out by Scottish Ministers. However, the developers have previously been given the go-ahead by the local authority, going against the advice of Scottish Natural Heritage and the Scottish Environmental Protection Agency. This raises the question of how the SDG framework filters down to local governance.

Further reading

- Coul Links campaign: www.scottishwildlifetrust.org.uk/our-work/our-advocacy/current-campaigns/coul-links
- Scottish Environment LINK Fight for Scotland’s Nature: <https://www.fightforscotlandsnature.scot/>
- Scottish Wildlife Trust’s response to the Scottish Government’s consultation on post-Brexit environmental governance: www.scottishwildlifetrust.org.uk/2019/05/844823-fighting-for-scotlands-nature-after-brexit-scott-leatham

Author

Scott Leatham, Policy Specialist at the Scottish Wildlife Trust

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⁵ Stockholm Resilience Center. (2019) Planetary boundaries research . Online from <http://www.stockholmresilience.org/research/planetary-boundaries.html>

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⁸ RSPB et al. (2016) State of Nature 2016: Scotland. Online from http://ww2.rspb.org.uk/Images/StateOfNature2016_Scotland_1%20Sept%20pages_tcm9-424988.pdf

Promote peaceful and inclusive societies for sustainable development, provide access to justice for all and build effective, accountable and inclusive institutions at all levels

International Voluntary Service

The International Voluntary Service (IVS) was founded in 1931 by a group of leading peace activists who successfully lobbied the British Government to allow conscientious objectors to volunteer overseas in place of forced military conscription. IVS has retained the focus of our founders by promoting volunteering as a mechanism by which to build peace and understanding between communities. In 2017, IVS published a 5-year strategic plan that placed SDG 16 at the heart of the organisation and ensures that all our activities align with the Targets associated with the Goal. All new projects must specifically address one of the SDG 16 Targets or Indicators. A recent example would be our Young Trustee programme which aims to reduce the average age of Trustees in Scotland. The project is addressing Goal Target 16.7 – to ensure responsive, inclusive, participatory and representative decision-making at all levels.

How is Scotland doing against this Goal?

Goal 16 was one of the most contentious elements of the 2030 Agenda, with some nations seeing it as a step by the United Nations towards a new framework of global government. Prior to being titled 'Peace, Justice & Strong Institutions', the Goal was referred to as the 'Good Governance Goal'. As a result of this unease from some UN members, the Goal had its targets somewhat diluted and some targets made intentionally vague. With a focus on Good Governance, Goal 16 is one of the more difficult SDGs to track. Furthermore, Scotland's position as a devolved nation further complicates progress-tracking. For example, Goal Target 16.5 focuses on measures to reduce corruption. However, global indexes such as Transparency International's Corruption Perception Index¹ only provide data on a UK level basis. There are also policy disagreements between the UK and Scottish Governments on areas specifically relevant to this Goal. An obvious example would be the Scottish National Party administration's support for the decriminalisation of drugs which is in stark contrast to the entrenched policy position held at Westminster.

This being said, Scotland is making significant progress on SDG 16 and can even be regarded as a leader on some key targets – especially violence reduction, the strengthening of national institutions globally, and participatory and representative decision-making. As an established developed nation, Scotland leapfrogs many nations on Goal 16 progress, with Goal Targets such as 16.9, 16.10 & 16.A easily reached by most developed nations. Furthermore, progress has been made on Targets 16.1 and 16.3. The former aims at 'significantly reduc[ing] all forms of violence and related death rates everywhere'. Figures released in 2018 showed that the homicide rate in Scotland has fallen to its joint lowest level since 1976.² This is a remarkable shift given that Scotland was named the most violent country in the developed world by a 2005 UN report.³ This success is attributed to the adoption of a public health approach to violence. The latter urges nations to 'promote the rule of Law at the national and International levels and ensure equal access to justice for all'. For Scotland, figures released in 2018 show that the rate of reconvictions has fallen by 22% since 2006/07 to a 19-year low.⁴ Internationally, the Scottish Government has developed ground-breaking initiatives such as the Climate Justice Fund⁵ and wrote the SDGs into the international development assistance agreement with Malawi.⁶ Furthermore, Scotland is leveraging the expertise of its national institutions such as NHS Scotland to share best practice, increase capacity and strengthen relevant institutions within partner countries.⁷ In 2017 the Scottish Government committed funding to a programme that seeks to train at least 50 women, every year until 2021, from international conflict zones in prevention and resolution of conflict.⁸ This programme follows the establishment of the Syrian Women's Advisory Board, a Scottish Government initiative that aimed to ensure female voices

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contributed to the Syrian Peace process. Scotland can also be seen as leader on Target 16.7 – ‘to ensure responsive, inclusive, participatory and responsive decision making at all levels.’ The ‘50/50 by 2020’ campaign from the Scottish Government’s Third Sector Unit aims to encourage organisations across all sectors to have a gender balance by 2020.⁹ 2018 was designated the ‘Year of Young People’ (YoYP) by the Scottish Government. A core objective of the celebration was to provide a platform for more young people to have their voices heard.¹⁰ The YoYP prompted organisations across Scotland to develop new ways to integrate young people into project design and led to the development of new initiatives such as the Young Trustee movement from IVS.¹¹ Furthermore, Scotland is a global leader on youth participation in democracy, having lowered the voting age to 16 in local elections and for the development of the Scottish Youth Parliament. SYP aims to provide a national platform for young people to discuss the issues that are important to them, and campaign to effect the change they wish to see. Key achievements include their advocacy work for ‘Votes at 16’ which ensured that young people aged 16 and 17 could vote in the Referendum on Scottish Independence in 2014. Another was the 2017-8 campaign ‘Right Here Right Now’, centred on improving the protection of young people’s rights in Scotland, which was successful in securing a commitment from the First Minister, Nicola Sturgeon, that the United Nations Convention on the Rights of the Child (UNCRC) would be incorporated into Scots Law.¹²

Is Scotland committed to achieving this Goal?

In 2018, IVS launched a campaign in the weeks preceding the UN’s International Day of Peace (21st September) to raise awareness of the Targets outlined within Goal 16 and the issues affecting Scotland. Bill Kidd MSP submitted a motion to debate Scotland’s progress towards the Goal in the Scottish Parliament. The motion received cross-party support and a debate took place on the 20th of September. Over 30 MSPs, from all major parties, took part in the discussion with a vote held to add additional time for the discussion. MSP’s from all major parties took part in the discussion. Furthermore, there is significant overlap between Scottish Government policy priorities and the Goal 16 Indicators. This is, for example, visible in the Government’s support of civil society initiatives such as Scotland’s Third Sector Governance Forum.¹³ In July 2015, the First Minister committed Scotland to the SDGs by mapping them to the National Performance Framework which, as a result, is now part of Scotland’s efforts to meet the Goals.¹⁴

What should Scotland do better to achieve this Goal?

Whilst not measuring the same indicators as the SDGs, the United Kingdom is one of the lowest-ranked developed nations on the Global Peace Index.¹⁵ In the past five years, the UK fell over 12 places in the rankings. This decline is mostly attributed to significant weapons exports, the UK’s prominence in external conflicts, and its stock of nuclear and heavy weapons. Further, large weapons platforms such as the new Queen Elizabeth Class aircraft carriers were built in Scotland, and the UK’s nuclear submarine fleet is based on Scotland’s west coast. This level of militarisation positions Scotland badly in relation to Target 16.1 which urges nations to ‘significantly reduce all forms of violence and related death rates everywhere’. Defence policy and spending are set by the UK Government, so it is difficult for the Scottish Government to bring about radical change on these issues. Further, the policy bottleneck caused by Brexit is limiting discussions on the UK’s upcoming Trident nuclear weapons replacement programme. Campaigners must continue to push for change in public opinion away from increasing military expenditure.

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Case study — reducing ‘violence as disease’

Scotland has come a long way since being labelled the most violent nation in the developed world in a UN report in 2005, with Glasgow branded the ‘Murder Capital of Europe’ by the World Health Organisation.¹⁶ The Scottish Violence Reduction Unit (SVRU) is a national centre of expertise in tackling violence. The unit was originally founded in 2005 by Strathclyde Police who began investigating different approaches to tackling violence. The SVRU adopted a public health approach which treats violence as a disease. This approach sees the Unit looking to diagnose and analyse the root causes of violence in Scotland. Since the founding of the SVRU, Scotland has seen homicides fall to their lowest level since 1976 with the latest figures showing a 39% decrease over the last decade.¹⁷ That being said, violence remains a chronic problem in Scotland, with domestic abuse and sexual violence a growing concern.¹⁸ The SVRU is funded by the Scottish Government with an annual budget of around a million Pounds in 2018. It is now advising police units across the UK and has supported the development of a similar unit in London in an attempt to combat rising knife crime in the city. The SVRU is an excellent example of research-based policymaking and is ensuring that Scotland is on track to meet the 2030 Goals.

Author

Chris Pettigrew, Fundraising Manager at the International Voluntary Service

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Strengthen the means of implementation and revitalize the global partnership for sustainable development

Business in the Community

Business in the Community (BITC) is the oldest and largest business-led membership organisation dedicated to responsible business. It was created nearly 40 years ago by HRH The Prince of Wales. It inspires, engages and challenges members and mobilises their collective strength as a force for good in society to create a skilled, inclusive workforce; build thriving communities in which to live and work; and to innovate to repair and sustain our planet. Business in the Community has a vibrant membership of hundreds of businesses, large and small, connected by the conviction that their success is inextricably linked to society's prosperity. In this way Business in the Community is built on the premise of Goal 17 – we build partnerships between organisations in every sector and of every size, collaborating and innovating to achieve the SDGs.

How is Scotland doing against this Goal?

In 2017, the Scottish Government hosted a conference on inclusive growth where the International Monetary Fund (IMF), Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) and other international organisations noted that Scotland had the size, resources and cross-sectoral commitment to take a leading role in achieving inclusive growth. In 2018, the Scottish Government refreshed its National Performance Framework and created eleven outcomes aligned to the SDGs. One of the purposes of this framework is to 'create sustainable and inclusive growth', and whilst this framework is applied to all public sector activities, it is also relevant for the private and third sectors. Within the framework two outcomes are mapped to Goal 17:

- 'We are open, connected and make a positive contribution internationally';
- 'We respect, protect and fulfil human rights and live free from discrimination'.

There are several partnerships that exist to support these outcomes with policy/political backing. In terms of the indicator on human rights, the Scottish Government has been working with BITC Scotland, Scottish Enterprise and the Scottish Human Rights Commission to develop a Business and Human Rights action plan. This would enhance the existing UK action plan on business and human rights by linking the devolved powers in Scotland and the local policy context. Regarding the outcome on 'being international', the latest National Economic Forum, held in May 2019, was focused on Scotland's new trade plan which concentrated on increasing export and supporting businesses to trade on a global stage. The Scottish Government is also partnering with Iceland, New Zealand and the OECD on a 'Wellbeing Economies' project.² This project supports partnership working, but also Goal Targets 7.4 (Enhancing policy coherence for sustainable development), 17.6 (Enhance the global partnership for sustainable development), 17.17 (Encourage effective partnerships), and 17.19 (Further develop measurements of progress). In addition, the Scottish Council of Voluntary Organisations received funding to organise the SDG Network,³ open to all organisations but with a focus on the third sector. This network has enabled members, both individual and organisational, to share insights, collaborate on activities, and build partnerships to support the delivery of the Goals.

In the private sector, the Scottish Environmental Protection Agency, Standard Life Aberdeen, and the Institute of Chartered Accountants of Scotland created a Business Reporting on the Global Goals network. Its objective is collaboration to improve and increase business incorporating the Goals into their annual reporting. Business in the Community launched a new campaign called 'Waste to Wealth'⁴ which challenges organisations to, among other things, 'work collectively towards doubling the nation's

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productivity and eliminate avoidable waste by 2030'. So far, over 100 organisations have signed up to this commitment, many of these have operations in Scotland. All these activities support partnerships within and between sectors to promote the Goals. In terms of impact already achieved, there has been a noticeable increase in the recognition of the SDGs by organisations and of their attempts to incorporate these into their own strategies and activities.

Is Scotland committed to achieving this Goal?

The Scottish Government has made a strong effort to engage with the SDGs overall. They have encouraged engagement from businesses in their policy development, including their Fair Work Action Plan and the review of the Scottish Business Pledge. The alignment of the National Performance Framework with the Global Goals enables more partnerships to use a common framework to map their activity. There is a real spirit of collaboration between business and Government to promote inclusive growth and the SDGs. However, measuring impact is difficult as these partnerships tend to promote and support all the other Goals and because the initiatives discussed have only recently been published or are still in progress. There could always be more political will and focus given to true, strategic partnership working between business and government, however the political and policy environment in Scotland is positive to supporting Goal 17 and the rest of the SDGs. Scotland could also do more to engage businesses, especially small businesses, in the Goals. This could be done, for example, through the refreshed Scottish Business Pledge, and we hope that this will be the case.

What should Scotland do better to achieve this Goal?

Partnerships take time and continuous effort to build and maintain, and therefore it is essential to keep a focus on the SDGs. Especially with the uncertainties around Brexit, it is paramount that the current culture of partnership work is maintained in Scotland. There also needs to be a deepening of existing relationships, moving beyond the Goals to their individual targets, with specific actions identified. One method for doing this would be to ensure all government contracts and grants clearly map to the National Performance Framework and by extension to the SDGs. Also, they should identify which Goal Targets they are working to support and how. This would increase transparency and show the true power of partnership working. The Scottish Government would need to initiate this policy change, but the partnership would need to be equal between business, government and the third sector to be truly impactful.

Case study — challenging perceptions of mental health through partnership

'This Is Me Scotland' is a joint initiative between PwC, Barclays, Business in the Community Scotland, the Scottish Association for Mental Health, and Samaritans Scotland.⁵ It aims to change perceptions of mental health by encouraging businesses to follow a set of guidelines which encourage discussion and support. The initiative complements existing Scottish Government policies such as See Me and NHS Scotland's Healthy Working Lives programme. The organisations signed up to this commitment employ tens of thousands of people in Scotland. The campaign has now had two public events with significant numbers in attendance, and between events is providing free resources for organisations of all sizes and in all sectors to take practical actions that will improve mental health and wellbeing in their workplaces. The campaign directly supports SDG 3 on good health and wellbeing, and especially Goal Target 3.4 – 'By 2030, reduce by one third premature mortality from non-communicable diseases through prevention and treatment and promote mental health and well-being'. But this campaign and its achievements are only possible because of the

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partnership between different sectors, organisations within sectors, and organisations operating across different geographies. The initiative also makes use of global learning and solid data management to inform the actions that people take to improve mental health and wellbeing.

Author

Dr Cynthia Marks, Senior Manager Operations & Policy at Business in the Community Scotland

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Strengthen the means of implementation and revitalize the global partnership for sustainable development

Scotland's International
Development Alliance

Scotland's International Development Alliance

Scotland's International Development Alliance is Scotland's only umbrella organisation representing organisations and individuals working in international development. We endorse the SDGs and align our objectives to them. We ask all our 170+ members to do the same. Goal 17 is of specific importance to us as an internationally focused membership body, because the Goal Targets relate specifically to global partnership and cooperation in areas such as international development finance, global trade and tax systems, technology and capacity building. The Alliance attempts to work with the Scottish Government and others to make sure its policies in other areas reinforce development outcomes elsewhere.

How is Scotland doing against this Goal?

In a world that is more interconnected than ever before, working together, sharing ideas, and fostering innovation at all levels of society is both necessary and feasible. Key to this is the creation of space for such partnership and cooperation, both physical and virtual. Examples include partnerships between schools in different countries, North-South business partnerships, and networks linking the public, private and civil society sectors. As a devolved administration, Scotland is limited as to how much progress it can make against the targets under Goal 17. This is due to the fact many of these relate to reserved powers currently residing at UK level, such as overall aid and development finance, global governance and international trade. Nonetheless, within the scope that it has, we can say that Scotland's global role has no significant dis-alignment with SDG 17, and can be said to be progressing adequately within the limitations stated.¹ Specifically, available policies and documents provide evidence that cooperation and partnership (e.g. partnership agreements with recipient countries) are embedded in Scotland's international development programme. That said, although the powers to create fairer trade and investment rules (Goal Targets 17.10 and 17.12) lie outwith the powers of the Scottish Government, there may nonetheless be opportunities to actively promote fairer rules to other national governments as part of Scotland's own trade and investment strategy. Crucially, Goal 17 also includes a specific Target relating to 'policy coherence' (17.14), a concept that underpins the entire 2030 Agenda. It asks decision-makers to look at the economic, social and environmental aspects of sustainable development holistically, balancing tensions and competing agendas wherever possible. We believe Scotland can do much more and demonstrate global leadership on this issue. There is a commitment in the International Development Strategy² (as well as in Scotland's National Performance Framework and further related strategies) to policy coherence. However, a more detailed analysis of where policy incoherence might arise, and how key synergies might be leveraged, is not present.

Is Scotland committed to achieving this Goal?

Politically, there has been a very high level of commitment to the principles of Goal 17, particularly around partnership and cooperation in the Scottish Government's International Development Strategy and supporting policy documents. There has also been high-level political commitment to 'Beyond Aid' and 'Do No Harm' in reference to achieving better policy coherence in speeches by the First Minister and other Ministers, election manifestos, and various internationally oriented strategies and policy statements since 2016. The Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) make the case that political commitment is only one of eight key 'building blocks' for securing progress on SDG 17.14.³ However, using their suggested indicators to measure progress on these eight key elements, Scotland scores low on all elements. It also still scores low on political commitment as it lacks a 'formal institutional catalyst (inter-ministerial committee or

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centralised oversight body) that is mandated to promote better coherence for sustainable development'.⁴ Some work has been undertaken on specific thematic areas that reinforce Scotland's international development work, such as on climate and global citizenship education, but this work is not systematic and, although promising, only touches the iceberg in terms of ensuring better policy coherence.

What should Scotland do better to achieve this Goal?

A priority for Scotland should be to measure progress on international development. Crucially, the international outcome in the National Performance Framework (NPF) does not yet have a full set of indicators to measure progress in this area. We believe any indicator developed must go some way to measure coherence in relation to international development outcomes across the whole of government, as well as the development of specific measures. Nonetheless, the NPF has the potential to be genuinely groundbreaking in terms of its use to measure policy coherence for sustainable development. It has the potential to be a rigorous monitoring and reporting system that includes indicators for assessing the institutional mechanisms for coherence and screening of domestic and international policies that could adversely affect sustainable development in other countries. Furthermore, there are currently no systematic processes or mechanisms whereby the Scottish Parliament or any other publicly accountable body could scrutinise legislation, existing policy or new policy through a 'sustainable development' lens. To do this requires considering any given intervention's transboundary and transgenerational effects holistically. At a minimum, 'proofing' all legislation or policy through systematic scrutiny in this way would allow the Government to formally recognise any trade-offs that might exist between, for example, economic development and environmental degradation. This is an essential part of making progress on Goal Target 17.14, according to the OECD.⁵ But Scotland could go further. By developing a suite of publicly available screening tools and mechanisms used by all government teams to consider trade-offs and synergies between the policies in question and other sustainable development outcomes, the Scottish Government could be world-leading on Goal 17.

Case study – legislating and the developmental lens

With regards to climate change, although Scotland is now world-leading on its proposed targets, the new Climate Change Bill (at the time of writing) does not include climate justice principles which would require Ministers to consider impacts on developing countries when enacting this legislation. Furthermore, in the early stages of the legislative process for this new Bill, no analysis of international impacts of policies was undertaken. Had there been a formal mechanism whereby this legislation was developed and scrutinised through a sustainable development lens, the international impact analysis and climate justice principles would have been included in the process and Bill respectively. Furthermore, it is far more likely that the elephant in the room – Scotland's continued investment in North Sea oil – would be acknowledged or, better still, acted upon.

Further reading

- Scotland's Place in Building a Just World: <https://www.intdevalliance.scot/resources/scotlands-place-building-just-world>

Author

Lewis Ryder-Jones, Policy and Communications at the Scottish International Development Alliance

Strengthen the means of implementation and revitalize the global partnership for sustainable development

¹ Long, Graham. (2019) The SDGs and Scotland: a discussion paper and initial analysis (including alignment with National Performance Framework. SCVO. Online from <https://scvo.org.uk/policy-research/evidence-library/2019-the-sdgs-and-scotland-a-discussion-paper-and-initial-analysis-including-alignment-with-national-performance-framework>

² Scottish Government. (2016) Global Citizenship: Scotland's International Development Strategy. Online from <https://www.gov.scot/publications/global-citizenship-scotlands-international-development-strategy/>

³ OECD. (2018) Policy Coherence for Sustainable Development 2018: Towards Sustainable and Resilient Societies. Online from https://read.oecd-ilibrary.org/development/policy-coherence-for-sustainable-development-2018/eight-building-blocks-for-coherent-implementation-of-the-sdgs_9789264301061-5-en#page4

⁴ OECD. (2018) Policy Coherence for Sustainable Development 2018: Towards Sustainable and Resilient Societies. Online from https://read.oecd-ilibrary.org/development/policy-coherence-for-sustainable-development-2018/tracking-progress-in-policy-coherence-for-sustainable-development_9789264301061-7-en#page4

⁵ *ibid.*

Annex – The reporting template

SDG Goal X:

Please use this template for your contribution to the 'snapshot review' of how Scotland is performing against the UN Sustainable Development Goals. If you need to write more than the word limits indicate, please feel free to do so! Please also insert graphs or tables. Should you have questions, please contact Oxfam Scotland. Thank you for your contribution to the review.

Organisation and author details (around 100 words)

Below, please provide a description of your role in your organisation and how your organisation is involved with this Goal. Please also insert your organisation's logo if you allow it to be used in the snapshot review.

From your perspective, how is Scotland doing against this Goal? (around 300 words)

Below, please write about progress or the lack of it towards achieving this Goal from your own perspective. Identify key data when making your assessment and try to give the reader the story beyond the numbers. Where relevant, please write about who or what is most at risk if this Goal is not achieved and what impact this might have.

What do you think about the current level of political and policy commitment to achieving the aims of this Goal in Scotland and the level of impact this is having? (around 200 words)

Below, please state your view on whether there is a sufficient level of commitment and identify any initiatives put in place, and by whom, as well as the difference you believe these are making.

What should Scotland do better to achieve this Goal? (around 300 words)

Please write about what you think should be done to achieve this Goal. Be explicit about who you think should take the lead in making improvements – government, business, third sector? If you can, give an example of a project or a policy – also from other countries – that could help Scotland to make progress .

Case study (around 300 words)

Below, please write about an example of how the policy problem is having an impact in Scotland, from your perspective and that of your organisation.

Further reading (no word limit)

Please, identify further information and resources on this Goal and to your work in this area.

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